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¹https://www.perfsonar.net/deployment_models.html

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
API	Application Programming Interface
CHIL	Controller Hardware-in-the-loop
CIDR	Classless Inter-domain Routing
CPTe	Cumulative Power Tracking Error
CR	Custom Resource
CRD	Custom Resource Definition
DRTS	Digital Real-Time Simulator
dq	Direct Quadrature
FMI	Functional Mock-up Interface
FMU	Functional Mock-up Unit
GD-HIL	Geographically Distributed Hardware-in-the-loop
GD-PHIL	Geographically Distributed Power Hardware-in-the-loop
GD-RT	Geographically Distributed Real-time
GD-RTS	Geographically Distributed Real-time Simulation
GM	Gain Margin
GPIO	General Purpose Input/Output
GPS	Global Positioning System
HIL	Hardware-in-the-loop
HuI	Hardware under Investigation
HuT	Hardware under Test
IA	Interface Algorithm
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICE	Interactive Connectivity Establishment
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IT	Information Technologies
ITM	Ideal Transformer Model
IP	Internet Protocol
LV	Low voltage
MIMO	Multiple Inputs, Multiple Outputs
MIPTE	Maximum Instantaneous Power Tracking Error
MuI	Model under Investigation
MU	Mobile Unit
NAT	Network Address Translation
NTP	Network Time Protocol
OS	Operating System
PF	Power Factor
PGP	Pretty Good Privacy
PHIL	Power Hardware-in-the-Loop
PM	Phase Margin
PPS	Pulse-per-Second
PTP	Precision Time Protocol
RI	Research Infrastructure
RiasC	Research Infrastructure as Code
RMS	Root Mean Square
RT	Real time
RTC	Real-time Clock
RTDS	Real-time Digital Simulator

SBC	Single Board Computer
SIL	Software-in-the-loop
SISO	Single Input, Single Output
SuI	System under Investigation
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
TURN	Traversal Using Relays around NAT
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
VM	Vector Margin
VPN	Virtual Private Network
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

Executive Summary

This work related to improved and extended real-time and co-simulation as well as Hardware-in-the-loop experiments covers a broad range of different but related topics, with a common focus on the interconnection and integration of Research Infrastructure in the form of simulators as well as physical laboratory equipment applied to:

- Multi-domain co-simulation,
- Mixed continuous and event-based co-simulation,
- Local and remote Hardware-in-the-loop testing,
- Virtual interconnections of multiple physical laboratories, and
- Virtual interconnections of multiple real-time simulators.

Due to the broad range of topics covered in the work plan and the large number of partners involved, it was necessary to start with a more precise definition of the work scope. For this purpose, a survey was made among partners, asking for interests and experiences in seven different topic areas to identify clusters with enough interest. The results were then compiled into a scoping proposal. An online workshop was held with all involved participants in order to formulate concrete research topics, and subsequently to define goals and intermediate steps for each of these topics.

The work related to multi-domain co-simulation aims at furthering the state-of-the-art in this field to enhance usability, flexibility, performance, standards compliance, and reproducibility of related approaches. Moreover, the work on real-time coupling and Hardware-in-the-loop-based testing aims at improving, analysing, and evolving methods and algorithms for coupling real-time systems – physical or simulated – with a particular focus on systems whose components are geographically distributed.

This report summarises related methods and tools developed in ERIGrid 2.0 focusing on concept development rather than implementation and proof-of-concept. The latter will be the subject of other, project-related reports.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This work related to improved and extended real-time and co-simulation as well as Hardware-in-the-loop experiments covers a broad range of different but related topics, with a common focus on the interconnection and integration of Research Infrastructure (RI) in the form of simulators as well as physical laboratory equipment applied to (cf. Figure 1):

- Multi-domain co-simulation,
- Mixed continuous and event-based co-simulation,
- Local and remote Hardware-in-the-loop testing,
- Virtual interconnections of multiple physical laboratories, and
- Virtual interconnections of multiple real-time simulators.

Figure 1: Possible coupling modes between Research Infrastructures (highlighted in green are the modes which are the primary focus of this report).

This document describes the methodical and technical background for the activities related to multi-domain co-simulation and real-time coupling as well as HIL-based testing focusing on concept development rather than implementation and proof-of-concept. The latter will be the subject of other, project-related reports.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The remainder of this document is organised as follows: Section 2 provides an introduction to, and the reasons for, the scoping and organisation of this work, spanning across eight loosely connected work tracks. The following Sections 3 and 4 then discuss the main results of this work related to multi-domain co-simulation and real-time coupling and HIL-based testing, respectively. Section 5 provides a high-level summary and conclusion.

2 Scope and Organisation of Work

2.1 Topics Scoping

Due to the broad range of topics covered in the work plan and the large number of partners involved, it was necessary to start with a more precise definition of the work scope. For this purpose, a survey was made among partners, asking for interests and experiences in seven different topic areas to identify clusters with enough interest:

- Different coupling pairings (lab-lab, lab-simulator etc.),
- Infrastructure for supporting message passing (i.e. event-based data) along with numerical data such as measurements,
- Accuracy and stability of co-simulation and Hardware-in-the-loop setups,
- Methods for the validation of results from coupled infrastructures,
- Communication standards for coupling,
- Multi-domain simulation, and
- Test system initialisation.

The results were then compiled into a scoping proposal. An online workshop was held with all involved participants in order to formulate concrete research topics, and subsequently to define goals and intermediate steps for each of these topics. At the end of this process, eight specific work tracks were defined, the first three related to multi-domain co-simulation and the remaining five covering real-time coupling and HIL-based testing approaches:

Track 1.1: Co-simulation of Alternating Current (AC) grids and Information Technologies (IT) networks

Track 1.2: Co-simulation of AC grids and heat networks

Track 1.3: Co-simulation initialisation

Track 2.1: Time delay compensation and bandwidth estimation

Track 2.2: Improving stability of HIL simulation

Track 2.3: Sensitivity analysis based on mathematical modelling

Track 2.4: Applicability of different Real time (RT) methods for validation

Track 2.5: Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling

Background information on these topics as well as results from all work tracks are collected in subsequent sections of this report.

2.2 Sprint Concept

Even before detailing the scope of this work, it was evident from the work plan, that it would have some rather specific characteristics:

- A large number of participating partners, with a wide range of committed resources.

- A significant number of parallel activities which would not necessarily be closely related, due to the wide range of topics covered by this work.
- The need to produce tangible results which could be fed into the “demonstration pipeline” of the follow-up activities in the project.

Due to these circumstances, a number of challenges related to work execution could be foreseen:

- Partners with limited resources would risk depleting their work capabilities before any tangible results could be achieved, thus losing an opportunity for publication, etc.
- Partners with large resources might find themselves in a work track which would eventually run out of steam due to the depletion of all collaborators’ work capabilities. At this point, it might not be easy to contribute to another track.
- Without track-specific milestones, there would be a risk of work being deferred towards the end of the respective work task.

In order to meet these challenges, it was decided to organise this work around an approach inspired by – and adapted from – agile software development. In agile development, one of the key mantras is to “release often”, i.e., to produce incremental improvements of the product on a frequent basis. This is often achieved by a series of “sprints”, short periods where a development team works towards an incremental goal. This allows a complex goal to be broken down into limited, well-defined and testable subgoals.

In agile development, sprint periods are often very short, from a few weeks down to a few days. This was not considered to be well-suited to the exploratory nature of research work; the initial sprint length was therefore chosen to be four months. This would allow partners with few resources to focus their contributions.

3 Multi-domain Co-simulation

3.1 Background

The energy transition and associated developments in the modern-day energy system, such as the deployment of electric vehicles, digital and Power-to-X technologies are driving a paradigm shift in system operations. This creates a need for advanced modelling and simulation capabilities to study the complex interactions between multiple domains.

Co-simulation has emerged as a popular method to analyse such complex system behaviour by integrating multiple domain-specific tools/simulators into a joint simulation setup. Thereby, a system or model is decomposed into a set of subsystems, each of which is simulated using a dedicated simulation engine or solver. However, the coherent integration of the subsystem simulators is not straightforward if the subsystems represent different domains with diverse underlying dynamics and behaviours. For example, continuous-time systems may have to interact with discrete-time systems, the relevant phenomena in two different domains may occur at time scales several orders of magnitude apart, or the subsystems may turn out to be cyclically dependent. While conceptual solutions exist for many of these challenges, many interesting research questions remain regarding their practical application.

This work aims at furthering the state-of-the-art in multi-domain co-simulations to enhance their usability, flexibility, performance, standards compliance and reproducibility. Following the outcome of an ad-hoc scoping workshop held by the ERIGrid 2.0 consortium, it has been divided into three work tracks:

- *Track 1.1 “Co-simulation of AC grids and IT networks”*: The goal of this track is the co-simulation of AC grids and Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) networks based on the latest Functional Mock-up Interface (FMI) 3 standard which – unlike its predecessor – is now able to address the needs of event-driven systems. Hence, this track develops FMI 3-compliant interfaces for network simulators and integration with a power system simulator using Mosaik 3 as a dedicated co-simulation framework. The resulting proof-of-concept will provide a complete FMI-compliant co-simulation setup for AC power systems and ICT networks.
- *Track 1.2 “Co-simulation of AC grids and heat networks”*: This track aims to accelerate the participation of project partners in the research and development of multi-energy systems and sector coupling. This will be achieved by developing a reference implementation of the multi-energy benchmark scenario from previous project work which can then serve as a basis for a tutorial.
- *Track 1.3 “Co-simulation initialisation”*: This track aims to address a number of specific research challenges surrounding the configuration and initialisation of co-simulation test setups. This involves bridging the gap between multi-scale and multi-domain setups and the desire to handle (configure, invoke, and execute) these in a coherent, user-friendly manner.

Each of these work tracks is described in greater detail in the following sections.

3.2 Co-Simulation of AC Grids and IT Networks

3.2.1 Motivation

AC power systems with continuous time behaviour are often modelled using dedicated power system simulators as a set of non-linear and/or differential-algebraic equations. On the other hand, IT/communication networks are discrete, event-driven systems that are modelled using approaches such as queuing theory. Hence, a co-simulation between such entities with fundamentally different time bases is a challenging task (Lin, Veda, Shukla, Mili, & Thorp, 2012; Palensky, Widl, & Elsheikh, 2014; Palensky, Van Der Meer, Lopez, Joseph, & Pan, 2017). To overcome some of the challenges, the FMI standard was adopted to facilitate tool-agnostic model exchange and co-simulation. However, version 2.0 of the standard is still limited when addressing advanced co-simulation issues. This especially pertains to event handling between Functional Mock-up Units (FMUs) as the interface does not bridge the gap between purely continuous-time models, and other systems such as discrete-event, data-flow, and state-machines (Broman et al., 2013). Subsequently, this has prompted the development of the FMI 3.0 standard to specifically address these issues (Junghanns et al., 2021).

3.2.2 Problem Statement

As stated earlier, the FMI 2.0 standard has limitations surrounding event-handling and discrete-event systems. This is better explained through the following example of an advanced co-simulation scenario involving 3 FMUs, as shown in Figure 2. FMU 1 represents a simple continuous-time system, described by the following ordinary differential equation:

$$f(u_1, u_2) = \frac{dy_1}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where u_1, u_2 are the inputs and y_1 is the output. The output y_1 is sent to a communication network, represented as a simple event queue where λ is the arrival rate, μ is the service rate, such that $\rho = \frac{\lambda}{\mu}$ represents the number of processed packets. Subsequently, the output of FMU 1, y_1 is transmitted to a controller, i.e., FMU 3 that generates a set point or control action, u_2 to be sent back to FMU 1. Thus, the entire co-simulation forms a closed-loop system that can be orchestrated by a co-simulation master algorithm. The current FMI 2.0 standard only allows all 3 FMUs in the above example to be treated as time-based simulators, i.e., all 3 FMUs are stepped in each time-step of the co-simulation. The standard does not accommodate stepping FMUs 2 and 3 only at specific time instances when an event is created. Such events can be generated by connected FMUs or internally via the event-based FMU. Hence, FMI 2.0 lacks the capability to handle such situations, as also noted in (Broman et al., 2013). This scenario is further complicated if the input of one FMU is dependent on the output of another event-based FMU, resulting in an algebraic loop. Hence, to overcome this, the FMI 3.0 standard proposes two dedicated modes, i.e., the event and step mode, as represented in Figure 3. Consequently, in this task, we aim to develop FMI 3.0 compliant FMUs to leverage these two modes in advanced co-simulation scenarios between continuous-time and discrete-event models.

3.2.3 Scope

Based on the above-mentioned motivation and problem statement, the scope of this task is broken down as follows:

Figure 2: Co-simulation example between multiple FMUs, to highlight the shortcomings of FMI 2.0.

Figure 3: State machine of the FMI 3.0 standard (Junghanns et al., 2021).

- Development of an FMI 3.0 compliant test FMU for a simple communication network simulator. This is modelled as an event queue, with a single input and output message.
- Implementation of a Python wrapper of the above FMU for co-simulation applications.
- Extend previously developed test FMU with multiple inputs and outputs.
- Application of developed FMU in a test case implementation using a dedicated co-simulation environment such as Mosaik 3. This involves building on previous work from ERIGrid.

3.2.4 Approach

The approach for the co-simulation of AC grids and IT networks in this track is based on the FMI 3 standard. Hence, the first step involved developing FMI 3-compliant FMUs of a simple communication network simulator. This is represented as an event-based queue/pipe with 2 possible variations: deterministic and probabilistic. Furthermore, each of these variations can have single input - single output or multiple inputs – multiple outputs. Variant A uses a classic event queue, where the time of the next event (i.e., message arrival) is known after inserting a new event (i.e., message sending). Accordingly, the next event time is determined in the *Event Mode*. In contrast, Variant B represents a dynamic event queue where the next event cannot be predicted, but has to be detected during simulation run-time through the *Step Mode*. The resulting test FMUs are visualised in Figure 4. Next, we apply the aforementioned developed FMUs in a test case implementation using a dedicated co-simulation environment, i.e., Mosaik 3. This involves a co-simulation between 3 FMUs representing a low-voltage distribution grid, a transformer tap controller, and the communication network simulator.

Figure 4: FMI 3 based test FMUs for communication network simulations.

3.2.5 Implementation

The co-simulation is implemented using the Mosaik 3 framework that acts as a co-simulation master. The overview of the entire setup is depicted in Figure 6. The power grid is modelled using pandapower and consists of a simple 4-bus system with two radial Low voltage (LV) nodes at 400 V, connected to a medium voltage slack bus at 20 kV. Both LV nodes consist of one load, each with a nominal rating of 3 kW and 0.96 kVar. The high voltage node is connected to the medium voltage node through a tap-changing transformer (0.25 MVA 20/0.4 kV) with tap positions $\in \{-3, 3\}$ for voltage regulation. The entire network is illustrated in Figure 5. The tap controller is modelled as a standalone Python script that implements a basic voltage regulation algorithm to maintain the bus voltages within a specified threshold. The entire co-simulation is summarised as follows. The ramping load block alters the values of the two loads, i.e. load 1 and 2, at every time step. Based on the load values, an AC power flow is then computed to calculate the resulting bus voltages. The voltages of the two load buses, i.e., v_3 and v_4 are then sent to the tap controller that computes the tap position of the transformer based on the received values to regulate the voltage of the system. The resulting tap position is then communicated back to the transformer via the same communication network.

3.2.6 Results

Results from the proof-of-concept setup described above can be seen in Figure 7. They show the response of the simulated system to a voltage drop at busbar 3 caused by an increase in load. Despite a new voltage reading being produced by the loadflow calculation every 500ms (green trace densely populated with triangular point markers), new values are only sent to the

Figure 5: Low voltage distribution grid modelled in pandapower. In this study, PV1 and PV2 are not considered.

Figure 6: Overview of co-simulation test setup based on Mosaik 3.

tap changer controller at a rate of once per minute (timestep multiples of 60,000). Consequently, the network simulator and tap changer controller components only operate after a new message is sent. This can be observed from the blue line markers (message received by tap changer controller) and the red markers (tap changer actuation).

Because the stages of the communication process are not discernible in Figure 7, Figure 8 presents the same data at a different zoom level, highlighting one message event around $t=60,000$. Here, the communication delay can be seen clearly. At $t=60,000$, a new voltage measurement is sent over the network (yellow marker and trace). It is then received by the tap changer controller at $t=60,500$.

Figure 7: Result plot from the co-simulation test. Green: Voltage at bus 3 as determined by the loadflow simulator. Yellow (invisible at this zoom level; see figure 8 below): Voltage measurement as sent over the communication network. Blue: Voltage measurement as received by the OLTC controller. Red: Resulting OLTC tap position.

Figure 8: Detail plot of one controller action. At this zoom level, the network delay can be seen between the changed voltage measurement being sent over the communication network at $t=60000$ (yellow) and the message being received at $t=60500$ (blue).

3.2.7 Further Work

The proof-of-concept described above is a working example of the correct mapping between the Mosaik API and the event concept of the FMI 3.0 standard. For the remainder work, it is planned to extend the simple FMI 3.0-based communication pipeline FMU into a configurable network simulator with multiple inputs and outputs. Subsequently, the integration of existing simulation tools such as ns-3 is planned.

3.3 Co-Simulation of AC Grids and Heat Networks

3.3.1 Motivation

In the past, research on multi-energy systems has mainly focused on matching supply and demand by optimizing either the scheduling or the operation of a large number of generation units (Mancarella, 2014). In contrast, the consideration of the impact on the associated infrastructure networks - the electrical grid, district heating network, gas infrastructure etc. - is a fairly new topic (Sorknæs, Lund, & Andersen, 2015; Lund, 2018). In particular, simulation-based technical assessments of multi-energy grids, where the main focus is on issues related to the operation and control of the grids themselves, remain a challenge. The reason for this is that available simulation tools typically only target one specific technical area (e.g., heat or power grids), as they are either the result of many years of academic research efforts in specific technical areas or have been developed by industry with a specific goal or for a specific target group. In recent years, work has already been done on the development of new tools and approaches for the integrated assessment of power and heat grids (Leitner, Widl, et al., 2019; Lohmeier, Cronbach, et al., 2020; Song, Hamacher, & Perić, 2021; Wirtz, Remmen, & Müller, 2021). The work in this track follows in these footsteps by further improving available tools and showcasing their applicability for the co-simulation of AC grids and heat networks.

Interest in the topic of modelling and analysing AC grids and heat networks has also been expressed by the project partners in an internal survey, in which 25 individual researchers participated. One main outcome of this survey was that even though there is relatively little experience among the project partners in modelling thermal systems, there is a keen interest in learning more about this subject and applying it to the analysis of multi-energy systems. Figure 9 shows selected results from this survey that confirm this outcome.

3.3.2 Problem Statement

The benchmark for multi-energy networks (*ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, 2021) developed earlier in the project, serves as the basis for this track. The primary goal was to implement co-simulation setups capable of analysing the corresponding test case. These co-simulation setups serve both as reference implementations as well as the basis for further training and tutorials.

The centrepiece for modelling the thermal domain of multi-energy networks are the simulators for the thermal network. They are crucial because the network state has a strong impact on the heat supply as well as the performance and operation of coupling points to other sectors (e.g., power-to-heat). Therefore, this track has focused on the further development of the following open-source tools:

Python package pandapipes The Python package *pandapipes* provides a network calculation tool for the analysis of district heating and gas systems (Lohmeier et al., 2020). It is implemented as an open source Python package (*pandapipes*, n.d.) and is developed at the Fraunhofer Institute for Energy Economics and Energy System Technology (IEE) and the University of Kassel. It utilizes the data analysis library *pandas* (*pandas – Python Data Analysis Library*, n.d.) and its functionality is closely related to the power systems calculation tool *pandapower* (Thurner, Scheidler, et al., 2018).

The *pandapipes* package focuses on the static analysis of balanced fluid systems. This en-

I already have experience in the modelling of ...

I would like to know more about the modelling of ...

I would like to learn more about the simulation of multi-energy systems, especially about ...

Figure 9: Selected results from an internal survey regarding multi-energy applications.

ables the static or quasi-static computation of temperature, pressure and velocity distributions in district heating networks. The applied algorithm for calculating the network state is referred to as *pipe flow*, in reference to the load flow calculations for electrical grids. The evolution of the network state with time can be calculated as consecutive snapshots of quasi-static thermo-hydraulic equilibrium states (steady-state operation).

Modelica library DisHeatLib The *DisHeatLib* is a library for the dynamic modeling of district heating networks (Leitner et al., 2019). It is implemented as an open-source Modelica library (*Modelica DisHeatLib library*, n.d.) and is developed at the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT). The DisHeatLib library uses the Modelica IBPSA Library as a core to provide

models specifically for district heating networks and relevant control systems. It also provides an interface to an optional electric power network.

The DisHeatLib library focuses on the analysis of thermo-hydraulic transients in fluid systems. This enables the analysis of dynamic effects in district heating networks, such as flow reversals or time-delayed propagation of fluid properties in the pipe system. The mass flow through all components is modeled using the so-called *plug flow* approach (van der Heijde, Fuchs, et al., 2017) with a non-linear pressure drop relation. Thanks to the balance equations of the underlying thermo-hydraulic model, components can be arbitrarily connected, including topologies with hydraulic loops or meshed networks.

3.3.3 Scope

Based on the above-mentioned motivation and problem statement, the scope of this task is broken down as follows:

- The pandapipes package was extended to perform quasi-dynamic heat distribution simulations, which compute dynamic temperature flows based on pandapipes' steady-state hydraulic mass flow calculations considering the thermal inertia of the system.
- The DisHeatLib library was extended to include a heat pump model that is adequate for coupling in a co-simulation with a power grid.
- The resulting co-simulation setups for the multi-energy network benchmark have been published and carefully documented to serve both as reference implementations as well as the basis for further training and tutorials.

3.3.4 Approach

The pandapipes package and the DisHeatLib library have been applied in the same simulation benchmark (*ERIGrid2/benchmark-model-multi-energy-networks: v1.0*, 2021) to showcase their advantages and challenges. This benchmark describes a reference setup for a multi-energy sector coupling application, where a power-to-heat facility provides a coupling point between a low-voltage distribution network and a local branch of a heating network. It comprises a thermal network, a LV power distribution grid and a power-to-heat facility. Figure 10a gives an overview of the overall system configuration. Figure 10b and Figure 10c give a more detailed view of the electrical and the thermal subsystems, respectively.

The chosen test case addresses issues related to self-consumption in a local energy community. It uses a simple voltage control scheme, which monitors the voltage levels in the power grid. The power consumption setpoint of the heat pump (controllable/flexible load) is adjusted to keep the voltage within acceptable limits. The thermal subsystem uses a dedicated controller scheme – referred to as *flex heat controller* – to operate the heating network and the power-to-heat facility. This controller decides whether the heat supply is covered entirely through the external grid or whether the power-to-heat facility supports by discharging the tank.

3.3.5 Implementation

The simulation benchmark intends to inspire the use of co-simulation for simulating multi-energy networks, where the different domains (power, heat, control) are covered by domain-specific

Figure 10: Overview of the system configuration of the multi-energy network benchmark.

simulation tools. Figure 11 visualizes a partitioning of the system under test into subsystems that can be implemented by dedicated simulators. However, this partitioning is only conceptual, as different implementations may choose to combine or further subdivide the depicted blocks, depending on the features of the used simulation tools.

Two implementations of the simulation benchmark have been developed, based on the Mosaik co-simulation framework. Both rely on pandapower (Thurner et al., 2018) for simulating the electrical subsystem and use stand-alone implementations of the controllers' logic in Python. However, the implementations differ in how they represent the thermal domain.

The first implementation uses the pandapipes package for simulating the thermal network. Dedicated stand-alone models in Python are used for those components of the thermal subsystem for which pandapipes offers no modeling support (consumer substations, heat pump and storage tank). They are linked via dedicated Mosaik wrappers and represented in pandapipes via valve controllers to regulate the mass flows, adjusting the pressure drops at the corresponding network valves to control the mass flows. In reference to Figure 11, this implements a

Figure 11: Conceptual breakdown of the system under test into simulated subsystems (thermal subsystems highlighted in yellow) for the multi-energy network benchmark.

more detailed partitioning, where the thermal network and the power-to-heat facility are each represented by two or more simulators².

The second implementation uses the DisHeatLib library for simulating the entire thermal subsystem, i.e., the thermal network and the power-to-heat facility. The DisHeatLib library (or the underlying IBPSA Library) provides models for all required components with the exception of the heat pump, for which a newly developed model is used. The complete model of the thermal subsystem is compiled to an FMU for co-simulation and linked with Mosaik. In reference to Figure 11, this implements a less complex partitioning, where the thermal network and the power-to-heat facility are together represented by just one simulator.

3.3.6 Results

Figure 12 shows a selection of results from the co-simulation setup using pandapipes (left column) and the DisHeatLib (right column), respectively. Figure 12a compares the temperature profiles at the supply line inlet (blue) and the return line outlet (green) of *consumer_1* as well as the network return line (orange). This shows that both implementations differ considerably in how they model the consumer (i.e., the temperature of the returned mass flow), but the resulting network dynamics are comparable both qualitatively and quantitatively. The same argument holds for the operation of the storage tank (cf. Figure 12b) and the heat pump (cf. Figure 12c). In contrast, Figure 12d shows that the computation of the pressure distribution fails with pandapipes in case more than one source feeds the network (i.e., when both the external thermal grid and the storage tank feed into the network's supply line). Wherever the pressure calcula-

²Three simulators are needed for the thermal network (pandapipes + 2 consumers) and two simulators for the power-to-heat facility (heat pump + tank).

tion does not fail, the comparison shows that the two approaches do not produce similar results, due to different assumptions regarding the pressure drop in the consumer models.

(a) Temperature profiles at supply line inlet (blue) and return line outlet (green) of *consumer_1* and network return line (orange).

(b) Temperature profiles in storage tank from top (orange), center (green) and bottom (blue) of the volume.

(c) Duration plot of heat pump power consumption with (orange) and without (blue) voltage control.

(d) Pressure profiles at return line outlet of *consumer_1*.

Figure 12: Comparison of simulation benchmark results for pandapipes (left) and the DisHeatLib (right).

3.3.7 Further Work

In the future, the limiting factors of both approaches are expected to be solved. With these expected improvements, both approaches will provide viable, robust and openly available tools for the modeling of the thermal domain of multi-energy networks. Furthermore, the new quasi-dynamic heat distribution simulation mode, which is based on the hydraulic calculations of pandapipes (assuming steady-state mass flows) plus a dynamic temperature flow computation considering the thermal inertia of the system, is planned to be published as a separate software package in the future. The new heat pump models for the DisHeatLib library will be made public as part of an official release.

Furthermore, both implementations will be used for tutorials and training as part of work package NA3. This will be a critical input to further training among the project partners, who expressed a keen interest in the subject of multi-energy system simulation (cp. Section 3.3.1 and Figure 9).

3.4 Co-Simulation Initialisation

3.4.1 Motivation

In the past decade, extensive research and development efforts have pushed the co-simulation paradigm from scattered proof-of-concepts towards unified platforms aiming at improved fidelity and better applicability. Improvements in fidelity have been achieved by the development of coupling mechanisms and master algorithms for various engineering domains (continuous models of physical systems, discrete model of ICT systems, discrete systems), whereas improvements in applicability have taken the form of cross-platform and cross-tool compatibility, standardisation and other changes to the overall user experience. However, along the road towards the widespread and straightforward usage of co-simulation in engineering design there are still challenges. A significant one is scalability, i.e. increasing the size and complexity of the system under simulation as well as the number of models and simulators the system is distributed across. Significant benefits could be achieved from developing a generic approach to complex co-simulation setups with an arbitrary number of models and simulators while maintaining a good user experience which can compete with alternatives such as high-fidelity domain-specific simulations or highly simplified approaches.

3.4.2 Problem Statement

A particular challenge that needs further attention in the context described above is the configuration, invocation, and generic initialisation of co-simulation setups. Without employing these in a generic way, scalability - and with it higher usability - cannot be achieved. This also (especially) applies to the energy domain in which the coupled models commonly have different typologies (continuous and discrete), data ownership constraints and vendor-specific simulation approaches. They also often exhibit *cyclic dependencies*. Cyclic dependencies are mutual couplings of one or more co-simulation components in which one (modelled) subsystem needs information from the next in order to calculate its impact on the other system, and vice versa. As co-simulations usually step in time and exchange variables sequentially, this leads to algebraic loops that need to be resolved properly both at the time of initialisation and at run time. An example for such a cyclic dependency is illustrated in Figure 13: A voltage-dependent load is connected at the end of a distribution grid feeder. The grid is represented by a load-flow model which is executed in one simulator, while the load is represented by a component model running in another simulator. Solving the grid model with an initial load $P_{load,n}$ yields the voltage $U_{load,n}$ at the connection point of the load to the grid. Subsequently solving the load model will yield an updated power value $P_{load,n+1}$ which in turn requires a recalculation of the grid model - and so on. A steady-state solution for voltage and power at the connection point of the load can only be found by iterating between the two models without advancing the simulation time.

3.4.3 Scope

The initialisation and configuration aspects of co-simulation setups are not a widely documented aspect of simulation engineering. Yet, the consortium experienced significant interest in this topic. As the work is primarily of an exploratory nature at this point, the scope has been defined accordingly:

1. Assess what configuration and initialisation issues have been experienced by consortium members in past and related research;

Figure 13: Example of a cyclic dependency in co-simulation

2. Categorise the issues and discuss which ones are in scope for ERIGrid 2.0;
3. Check what developments can be achieved within this track to resolve initialisation challenges;
4. Extend and improve existing approaches or develop new solutions; and
5. Discuss what co-simulations configuration challenges fit within project tasks that will start in the near future.

3.4.4 Approach

During the initial stages of the work, an online technical workshop was organised to discuss the scoping. Topics of interest concerning co-simulation initialisation involved:

Topological setup of co-simulations. That is, the steps that need to be taken to split system under test into multiple subsystem representations, each included into numerical models, attached to a numerical solver, and configured for runtime.

Invocation of model and simulation services. The steps the co-simulation engineer needs to undertake to configure, start, or stop a co-simulation and perform post-processing of results shall be largely agnostic to the implementation of the subsystem models. Examples within this topic include the co-simulation application interface (command line, GUI) and its Operating System (OS) dependency.

Coherent starting values of algebraic and state variables across the co-simulation. Given a co-simulation configuration, this entails a generic way of initialising the inner subsystem variables, differential or algebraic alike, as well as the interface variables between the subsystems of the system under test.

Aside from the main topics of interest, the scope was also marked by the focal domain-specific

and co-simulation tools applied in ERIGrid 2.0 (e.g., MOSAIK, FMI++). This, together with the 3 main topics has been discussed and included into a questionnaire issued to the consortium. This questionnaire provided the following, more concrete topics:

- Automatic scenario generation based on metadata in functional mockup units.
- Improved co-simulation sequence and sample handling.
- OS and version compatibility and dependency issues for co-simulation setups.
- Improved automatic testing of co-simulation experiments.
- Standardised post-processing sequences of co-simulation results.
- Bi-directional information flow within the co-simulation. Experimental setup, also at initialisation stage.
- Parametrization of the multiple scenario runs required to develop a scheme for simultaneously handling parameter sets and data.

After further discussion, it was decided to focus on co-simulation sequence and sample handling, both during runtime and initialisation time. This aligns well with recent developments in Mosaik, the focal co-simulation environment of this work. It has recently been improved with functionality to master cyclic dependencies using the *superdense time* approach with same-time loops (Cremona et al., 2017; Ofenloch et al., 2022).

3.4.5 Implementation

Cyclic dependencies are a challenge for the co-simulation scheduler: 2 or more subsystems are mutually dependent in their behaviour, which clashes with the sequential nature of scheduling algorithms. Naturally, this necessitates the simulation of subsystem A before it's outputs can be sent to the next simulator (B), which provides input to subsystem A again. For strongly coupled subsystems these causality problems can lead to undefined behaviour.

Mosaik 2 breaks loops by introducing artificial delays in simulation components, commonly 1 time step of the co-simulation scheduler, which allows one of the connected simulators to execute before the other using delayed inputs. It can be invoked by the `time_shifted` parameter. At initialisation time, however, the delayed inputs are by definition unknown, which necessitates the careful manual specification of the simulation component inputs, which is workable yet prone to mistakes.

The superdense time approach, which has been introduced in release version 3 of Mosaik (Ofenloch et al., 2022), allows simulators to iteratively exchange mutual data at their interfaces without having the scheduler incrementing the simulation time. In this fashion, (algebraic) interface variables can converge within a defined loop and hence resolving cyclic dependencies. Superdense time can be activated inside a simulator by setting a time of validity for the cyclic attributes. The approach is illustrated in Figure 14 and described in further detail in the Mosaik documentation³.

The superdense time approach can also be applied at initialisation time, i.e., when the scheduler has not incremented the simulation time at all. In that fashion, stable starting values of simulators (modelling subsystems of the co-simulation) can be achieved, especially state variables.

³<https://mosaik.readthedocs.io/en/latest/scheduler.html#same-time-algebraic-loops>

Figure 14: Visualization of superdense time (i.e., same-time loops) in Mosaik (Raub et al., 2021).

3.4.6 Results

The efficacy of the superdense time approach using same-time loops is illustrated using the multi-energy network benchmark model, which is elaborated in Section 3.3.4 and shown in Figure 10. The benchmark system has been implemented as a MOSAIK scenario. The boxes in Figure 15 show the simulation components (simulators), their mutual data flows, and causality. The orange arrows indicate cyclic dependencies, which are resolved by time-shifted connections in the original version of the benchmark. The highlighted blue boxes comprise the simulators coupled in a same-time loop using the superdense time approach in the adapted version of the benchmark. Their execution order in the same-time loop are indicated in the yellow-boxed upper right corners.

Figure 15: Visualisation of the Mosaik simulation scenario of the multi-energy benchmark using the same time loop approach. The orange numbers identify the execution ordering within the same-time loop.

For enhanced initialisation of this scenario, the (code within the) simulation components have been extended to support superdense time. Choosing which loops to include for the super-

dense time approach is still a manual operation, and overlooked (outer) loops may still cause unstable initialisation. For this specific scenario this implied that: 1) multiple simulators needed to be added to the same-time loop, 2) a separate initialisation attribute for the same-time loop simulators to indicate the initialisation is still going on was added, 3) a control function caching all the relevant same-time loop attributes was included in the domestic heating network (i.e., DHNetwork) for convergence checking, and 4) one connection was set to `weak`, i.e., the last one executed, in order to resolve the cyclic dependency in the same time loop.

The system has been tested by enabling/disabling the flexible heat controller (FlexHeatCtrl)–with and without using the same-time loops–and check the effects of the heat generation of the heat pump. The results are shown in Figure 16. Aside from the efficacy of the controller, which is showing plausible systemic behaviour, the application of the same time loop is also clearly distinguishable. The heat generation (controller enabled, orange line) starts uninitialised without a same-time loop implementation, while it initialised correctly –the visible spike at simulation start is a numerical artefact– when the same time loop is applied in the initialisation phase. This illustrates that the iterative initialisation is successful and entails a more accurate system response.

(a) Without same-time loop

(b) With same-time loop

Figure 16: Heat pump power consumption as simulated for one day; illustration of the same-time loop approach for enhanced co-simulation initialisation using MOSAIK.

3.4.7 Further Work

The current implementation with the new superdense time feature of Mosaik 3.0 applied to the multi-energy benchmark system was a complex test case for this feature and showed some opportunities for optimisation. Thus, some alterations in the code base of Mosaik were done and need further testing before the improvements can be officially released. Appropriate testing, implementation into the existing codebase and extensive documentation for future replication are seen as steps to be taken until the finalisation of this track.

Moreover, some of the configuration aspects that have been touched upon in the questionnaires and discussions will be transferred to the configuration management activity.

4 Real-time Coupling and Hardware-in-the-Loop Approaches

4.1 Background

This activity aims at improving, analysing and evolving methods and algorithms for coupling real-time systems – physical or simulated – with a special focus on systems whose components are geographically distributed. Following the outcome of the scoping workshop, work in the task has been divided into five work tracks:

- *Track 2.1 “Time delay compensation and bandwidth estimation”*: The goal of this track is to develop time delay compensation methods for geographically distributed PHIL systems. A particular focus of the work is on methods which don’t require high-precision clocks at both ends, utilising cheap hardware and/or statistics-based methods.
- *Track 2.2 “Improving stability and accuracy of HIL simulation”*: This track aims at analysing and improving interface algorithms for geographically distributed HIL systems, in order to achieve reliable and quantifiable coupling performance. Specifically, it focuses on two types of interface algorithms: direct quadrature (dq) and RMS-based approaches.
- *Track 2.3 “Sensitivity analysis based on mathematical modelling of PHIL simulation systems”*: This track is dedicated to the development of a framework for the sensitivity analysis of HIL systems. The framework will be experimentally validated as a proof-of-concept.
- *Track 2.4 “Applicability of different RT methods for validation”*: This track aims to expand the applicability of current validation methods for geographically distributed HIL systems to also include asynchronously coupled systems, i.e., systems where the signal delays are smaller than the time scale of the phenomenon under observation but much larger than the simulation time step.
- *Track 2.5 “Accelerating time-to-experiment for remote RI coupling”*: The goal of this track is to streamline the set-up of large-scale, multi-party distributed experiments. It develops a set of new tools which will allow to automate many aspects of the setup which currently have to be performed manually, a tedious and error-prone process. After proof-of-concept testing in this work, the toolset is planned to be used during the demonstration activities later on in the project.

Each of these work tracks is described in greater detail in the following sections.

4.2 Time Delay Compensation and Bandwidth Estimation

4.2.1 Motivation

Time delay is an inherent characteristic of any closed-loop PHIL setup affecting both accuracy and stability of the setup (Feng et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2021). As shown in Figure 17, the PHIL closed-loop stability margin degrades with the increment of the time delay, which destabilise the PHIL system once it exceeds a critical value. On the other hand, as analysed in (Feng et al., 2021), the time delay deteriorates the PHIL simulation accuracy and power transfer transparency between the simulation side and hardware side. High fidelity PHIL setups are conventionally realized through the compensation of time delay (Guillo-Sansano, Roscoe, &

Burt, 2015; Feng et al., 2020; Feng et al., 2021), which is variable yet deterministic for such setups (Guillo-Sansano, Syed, Roscoe, Burt, & Coffele, 2021).

Figure 17: Time delay impact on (a) PHIL system stability, (b) PHIL system accuracy regarding the power transfer transparency.

4.2.2 Problem Statement

Time delay compensation techniques for PHIL setups are well reported in the literature. Time delay in PHIL setups using a lead filter has been proposed in (Ren et al., 2011), and using a linear predictor for Geographically Distributed Power Hardware-in-the-loop (GD-PHIL) has been presented in (Liu et al., 2017). The accuracy of these compensation techniques (lead filter and linear predictor) is highly system dependent and do not perform well under variable delays; a comparison of performance can be found in (Feng et al., 2021). An alternative approach is to advance the phase of the interface signals by an amount equal to the time delay as proposed in (Guillo-Sansano et al., 2015; Feng et al., 2021). The proposed approach performs well and is not system dependent as long as the delay can be accurately quantified.

The renewed challenge is presented through the emergence of geographically distributed simulations where two or more Digital Real-Time Simulators (DRTSs) are interconnected over the Internet through a similar interface algorithm as utilised in PHIL setups as shown in Figure 18. The indeterministic nature of the exchange of data through the Internet presents a challenge for the determination of the time delay and its consequent compensation to realise high-fidelity simulations. This track looks at the development of time delay compensation methods for geographically distributed simulations.

4.2.3 Scope

The straightforward approach to determination of the time delay between two laboratories interconnected over the Internet is by the use of Global Positioning System (GPS) clocks interfaced

Figure 18: Configuration and implementation of the geographically distributed simulation.

with DRTS at either end, exchanging time-stamps for the calculation of the time delay. This offers precise calculation of time delay with precision of up to ns (subject to time synchronization of the GPS clock). While GPS time-stamped signal exchange presents a viable approach for the development of an accurate time-delay compensation method, the cost implications of high precision clocks can limit their deployment. With the availability of cheaper GPS modules for microcontrollers (such as for Raspberry Pi), this task will explore the synchronization performance assessment with high-precision synchronization available through industrial clocks.

This task also looks at development of alternative time delay compensation methods through use of statistical data of delays between the interconnected RIs. This requires the implementation of time delay logging between the RIs, Therefore, a network monitoring tool capable of determining the delays between the interconnected RIs is under development.

4.2.4 Approach

There are two approaches to time delay compensation in GD-RTS:

- *Time delay compensation implemented in feedback path:* Although there is a delay in the feedforward path and in the feedback path of the GD-RTS, the aggregate delay can be compensated for in the feedback path of the implementation. This approach is typically employed when one way latency cannot be determined, while a round-trip time can be determined. An example of such implementation is presented in Figure 19a, where there is only one GPS clock in Laboratory A (left side).
- *Time delay compensation implemented in both feed-forward and feedback path:* Where the one way latency can be calculated, the time delay compensation can be implemented in both the feed-forward and the feedback path as shown in Figure 19b. This presents a more accurate approach to time delay compensation as the time delay in the feed-forward path may be different from the time delay in the feedback path.

As is evident, the development of any time delay compensation requires the measurement of the time delay between the two research infrastructures. When data is exchanged between two research infrastructures, Laboratory A and Laboratory B, the two metrics for time delay can be defined as:

Figure 19: Overview of GD-RTS setups with different time delay compensation types

- *One-way latency*: The amount of time needed for a data packet to travel from Laboratory A to Laboratory B.
- *Round-trip latency*: The amount of time needed for a data packet to travel from Laboratory A to Laboratory B and back to Laboratory A.

The development of statistical or artificial intelligence-based methods to estimate time delays between research infrastructure requires the monitoring of additional performance metrics of the network that interconnects the RIs. The statistical/mathematical approaches can identify the intricate inter-dependencies of these metrics enabling better estimation of the time delay. A few additional quantitative and qualitative metrics can be defined to verify the behaviour of the network as summarised below:

- *Network capacity*: The amount of traffic that can cross between Laboratory A and Laboratory B.
- *Network utilisation*: The network capacity is currently in use.
- *Throughput*: The available network capacity that can be utilised.
- *Packet loss*: The number of packets lost when data is exchanged between Laboratory A and Laboratory B.
- *Jitter*: The variation in one-way latency or in round trip time between Laboratory A and Laboratory B.

The following section will introduce the network monitoring tool adopted to allow the gathering of the network performance metrics.

4.2.5 Implementation

An open source network measurement toolkit referred to as the performance Service-Oriented Network monitoring ARchitecture (perfSONAR)⁴ has been identified as a potential option for adoption. The software solution was developed and is maintained by a partnership of The Energy Sciences Network (ESNET), Pan-European Research and Education Network (GEANT) and academic institutions.

The toolkit offers a number of different models for its deployment⁵. Figure 20 shows the Mesh model adopted within the development. Each RI participating within a GD-RTS experimental setup will be part of a different network (campus network as in Figure 20). Establishing the mesh network between the RIs involves the installation of a perfSONAR node at each participating RI. A common shared configuration file defines the tests and their schedules that can be automatically read and executed by all the nodes within the network. The results can be stored in a central location or at any number of chosen participating nodes.

Figure 20: Network Monitoring Toolkit Deployment Model – Mesh⁶.

The results of the performance monitoring can be visualised using the Monitoring and Debugging Dashboard (MaDDash).

4.2.6 Results and Further work

The perfSONAR node is intended to be installed within a mobile unit, abiding by the architectural implementation adopted for wider tools being developed within the project. This implementation is currently in progress as part of Track 2.5.

⁴<https://www.perfsonar.net/index.html>

⁵https://www.perfsonar.net/deployment_models.html

Once the network monitoring tool has been established, the next steps would involve running the defined set of tests for a period and collect the data. This data will be utilised to develop the statistical approaches to time delay compensation and will be reported in the subsequent deliverable.

4.3 Improving Stability and Accuracy of HIL Simulation

4.3.1 Motivation

HIL simulations have evolved into a widely approved technique accelerating the verification of novel control and power technologies, and thus are being increasingly applied in the power and energy systems field for equipment testing. The verification of control devices can be implemented with the interconnection of a DRTS and the control device in a Controller Hardware-in-the-loop (CHIL) setup (cf. Figure 21a). On the other hand, for the validation of power hardware components, a PHIL setup is required based on which real hardware (Hardware under Test - HuT) is interfaced to the DRTS (cf. Figure 21b). A typical PHIL test setup consists of the DRTS, in which the power system is simulated in real-time, the power interface or amplifier, which links the hardware and the simulated system and the hardware power component, which can vary from a simple load up to an active device like a converter or diesel generator.

Figure 21: Conceptual visualization of the various types of HIL simulations.

Additionally, the modern power and energy systems (and further than that), which are moving towards decentralisation and digitalization, have motivated the interconnection of multiple RIs, thus effectively reducing the technological and manpower limitations of single facilities. This has led to the notion of GD-RTS, where the system under investigation is split into two or more subsystems, implemented at different DRTS systems at geographically dispersed laboratories, significantly increasing the capabilities for performing different test cases (cf. Figure 21c). Since as will be highlighted in the following sections, stability and accuracy issues arise in the implementation of the aforementioned setups, this track will focus on improving the stability of both PHIL and Geographically Distributed Hardware-in-the-loop (GD-HIL) simulations, to provide an accurate means for validating modern power and energy systems' components and technologies.

4.3.2 Problem Statement

In Table 1, a brief list of publications discussing the stability and accuracy of PHIL setups is presented:

Table 1: Relevant publications on stability and accuracy of PHIL setups.

Ref	Authors	Title	Year
(Guillo-Sansano et al., 2021)	E. Guillo-Sansano, M. H. Syed, A. J. Roscoe, G. M. Burt and F. Coffele	Characterization of Time Delay in Power Hardware in the Loop Setups	2021
(Pokharel & Ho, 2021)	M. Pokharel and C. N. M. Ho	Stability Analysis of Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Architecture With Solar Inverter	2021
(Lauss & Strunz, 2020)	G. Lauss and K. Strunz	Accurate and Stable Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) Real-time Simulation of Integrated Power Electronics and Power Systems	2020
(Langston, Szymanski, Schoder, Steurer, & Roberts, 2020)	J. Langston, T. Szymanski, K. Schoder, M. Steurer and R. Roberts	Practical Estimation of Accuracy in Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulation Using Impedance Measurements	2020
(Lundstrom & Salapaka, 2020)	B. Lundstrom, M. Salapaka	Optimal Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Interfacing: Applying Modern Control For Design and Verification of High-Accuracy Interfaces	2020
(Alenius et al., 2020)	H. Alenius et al.	Hardware-in-the-Loop Methods for Stability Analysis of Multiple Parallel Inverters in Three-Phase AC Systems	2020
(Lauss & Strunz, 2019)	G. Lauss and K. Strunz	Multirate Partitioning Interface for Enhanced Stability of Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Real-Time Simulation	2019
(Kotsampopoulos et al., 2018)	P. Kotsampopoulos, D. Lagos, N. Hatzargyriou, M. O. Faruque, G. Lauss, O. Nzimako, P. Forsyth, M. Steurer, F. Ponci, A. Monti, V. Dinavahi, K. Strunz	A Benchmark System for Hardware-in-the-Loop Testing of Distributed Energy Resources	2018
(Riccobono, Liegmann, Pau, Ponci, & Monti, 2017)	A. Riccobono, E. Liegmann, M. Pau, F. Ponci and A. Monti	Online Parametric Identification of Power Impedances to Improve Stability and Accuracy of Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulations	2017
(Markou, Kleftakis, Kotsampopoulos, & Hatzargyriou, 2017)	A. Markou, V. Kleftakis, P. Kotsampopoulos and N. Hatzargyriou	Improving existing methods for stable and more accurate Power Hardware-in-the-Loop experiments	2017

(Maniatopoulos, Lagos, Kotsampopoulos, & Hatziargyriou, 2017)	M. Maniatopoulos, D. Lagos, P. Kotsampopoulos, N. Hatziargyriou	Combined control and power hardware in-the-loop simulation for testing smart grid control algorithms	2017
(Lauss et al., 2016)	G. F. Lauss, M. O. Faruque, K. Schoder, C. Dufour, A. Viehweider and J. Langston	Characteristics and Design of Power Hardware-in-the-Loop Simulations for Electrical Power Systems	2016
(Kotsampopoulos, Lehfuss, Lauss, Bletterie, & Hatziargyriou, 2015)	P. C. Kotsampopoulos, F. Lehfuss, G. F. Lauss, B. Bletterie and N. D. Hatziargyriou	The Limitations of Digital Simulation and the Advantages of PHIL Testing in Studying Distributed Generation Provision of Ancillary Services	2015
(Barakos, Kotsampopoulos, Vassilakis, Kleftakis, & Hatziargyriou, 2014)	D. Barakos, P. Kotsampopoulos, A. Vassilakis, V. Kleftakis and N. Hatziargyriou	Methods for stability and accuracy evaluation of Power Hardware In the Loop simulations	2014
(Guillo-Sansano, Roscoe, Jones, & Burt, 2014)	E. Guillo-Sansano, A. J. Roscoe, C. E. Jones and G. M. Burt	A new control method for the power interface in power hardware-in-the-loop simulation to compensate for the time delay	2014
(Dargahi, Ghosh, & Ledwich, 2014)	M. Dargahi, A. Ghosh and G. Ledwich	Stability synthesis of power hardware-in-the-loop (PHIL) simulation	2014

Indeed, the applicability of HIL setups is mainly driven by their stability and accuracy properties, since the required interfacing components and techniques would be absent in a purely hardware validation. In particular, stability and accuracy are much deteriorated due to the effect of the inherent delays of HIL setups as well as the effects of the interface algorithm, when splitting of a power system needs to take place.

In a PHIL setup, the most important associated delay happens in the power amplification stage and the simulator time step, while the transmission of information between the two systems does not suffer from significant delays. As one would expect, similarly to PHIL simulations, the applicability of GD-RTS is also shaped by the stability and accuracy properties of the setup. Comparing GD-RTS and PHIL setups, the former differ to the latter in the three following ways: (i) GD-RTS setups suffer from larger time delays due to the geographical distance of the participating RIs, (ii) a PHIL simulation always requires the existence of a power amplifier, and (iii) the interfacing between the DRTS devices in a GD-RTS needs to happen through DC signals, because instantaneous time domain quantities has been shown to be inappropriate for packet based communications over the Internet (M. H. Syed et al., 2021).

To deal with those issues, advanced Interface Algorithms (IA) were investigated and verified, aiming to suggest new methods for improving the stability and the accuracy of such HIL simulations.

4.3.3 Scope

The scope of this Track can be understood from the contents of the four (4) distinct sprints, in which the overall work was split into. In the 1st sprint, the literature review discussed above was performed. Then, in the 2nd sprint, the investigation and simulation of existing approaches was performed, leading to the problem statement described in the previous subsection. Finally, during the 3rd and 4th sprints, further analysis and preliminary experimental validation of existing approaches as well as proposal of new ones is still taking place. In particular, in the next chapter of this Deliverable, the first suggested methodologies originating from sprint 3 will be reported, where stability and accuracy of GD-HIL setups are addressed and analysed. In more

detail, two approaches presented in literature, namely the synchronous coupling approach using direct-quadrature-zero ($dq0$) transformation and the asynchronous coupling approach using root mean square (RMS) are studied, while the stability and accuracy of GD-RTS setups are investigated to establish its practical applicability. This work has been also extensively reported in paper (M. Syed et al., 2022) and is a common outcome of this track and Track 2.4. Ongoing work from the 4th sprint, regarding the stability and accuracy of PHIL setups is briefly discussed in the next chapter and will be further reported in following deliverables.

4.3.4 Approach

In this track, focus was placed on investigating interface algorithms that improve stability and accuracy in both GD-RTS and PHIL simulations. The work was split into two phases:

- Two approaches presented in literature have been studied as candidates for interface algorithms in GD-RTS. These were the synchronous coupling approach using direct-quadrature-zero ($dq0$) transformation and the asynchronous coupling approach using root mean square (RMS). Initially, an advanced stability analysis was performed since it was shown that the conventional one cannot accurately predict the system response. For a complete and coherent analysis and in order to verify the stability findings from the mathematical modelling, a virtual GD-RTS was performed. As a final step for the verification of the proposed methods, a real world GD-RTS experimental setup was established between University of Strathclyde and National Technical University of Athens (ICCS-NTUA). The results have been published in (M. Syed et al., 2022).
- Based on the findings of the research during the first phase, it was investigated whether the dq -based approach can be modified and applied as part of the interface algorithm of PHIL setups, in order to facilitate the minimization or even elimination of the effect of the inherent delays, by enabling the use of time delay compensation. Additionally, it was investigated how other proven methods for improving stability and accuracy can be combined together with the delay compensation in the $dq0$ frame. The goal was to synthesise an advanced interface algorithm which would yield system properties very close to an ideal connection, where the power system is directly interfaced to the hardware without any intermediate stage. To achieve this, feedback filters and shifting impedance methods were considered. The research led not only to the combination of all of the previously mentioned three methods but also to the conception of improvements that facilitate the laboratory implementation of PHIL setups. More information is presented in the subsequent sections.

4.3.5 Implementation of the GD-RTS Investigation

To split one system into two subsystems, with each one being simulated at a different geographical location, i.e. to set up a GD-RTS experiment, a proper coupling mechanism needs to be devised. In particular, such an Interface Algorithm (IA) needs to take into consideration the accuracy and the stability of this GD-RTS system, which is subject to significant communication delays. As is also true in the PHIL case, a vast amount of such IAs can be found in the literature, with the majority of them being based on the voltage type ideal transformer model (V-ITM). Here, the connection point voltage of Subsystem 1 is reproduced at the Subsystem 2 through a controlled voltage source, and the currents of Subsystem 2 are reproduced at Subsystem 1 through a controlled current source.

Nevertheless, even though the implementation of this IA in a PHIL setup may seem relatively simple, the delays that characterise a GD-RTS system render it unsuitable for the exchange of sinusoidal signals. Hence, the extension of this IA to make it compatible with the setup under investigation seems unavoidable. This can be accomplished through a signal transformation (to DC quantities) and an appropriate reconstruction, before and after the transmission of the signals to be exchanged. In particular, in this track, two approaches will be considered: A synchronous coupling using direct-quadrature-zero ($dq0$) components and an asynchronous coupling using root mean square (RMS) components. The two methodologies are described in the following paragraphs.

Synchronous coupling approach using direct-quadrature-zero ($dq0$) To implement the V-ITM method, six signals have to be exchanged: three phase voltages from subsystem 1 in the feed-forward path (v_a , v_b and v_c) and three phase currents from subsystem 2 in the feedback path (i_a , i_b and i_c). In the approach described here, these are transformed into the $dq0$ frame, (v_d , v_q , and v_0) and (i_d , i_q and i_0) respectively, using first the Clarke transformation to obtain the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ components, and then the Park transformation to obtain the $dq0$ components. This yields the DC values at the steady-state. The voltage $dq0$ components of subsystem 1 are sent over the internet, thus a considerable amount of delay is introduced. When the $dq0$ are received at the other side of the communication channel interconnecting the two simulators (and subsystems) they are then transformed back to the natural abc frame. The difference in phase angle caused by the feed-forward time delay T_d^{ff} is compensated as:

$$\theta' = \theta + \Delta\theta = \theta + T_d^{ff} \cdot 2\pi f \quad (2)$$

Then the compensated abc voltages are used as setpoints for the controllable voltage source of subsystem 2. In the feedback path, the current $dq0$ components of subsystem 2 are sent back over the internet to subsystem 1. Again, the same procedure as for the feed-forward path is followed, and the currents are transformed back to abc components and compensated for the introduced feedback delay, T_d^{fb} . Finally, the compensated abc components are used as setpoints for the controllable current source of subsystem 1, and the loop of the whole system is closed. Of course, in order to keep the two subsystems synchronized, this approach necessitates the transfer of $\theta = \omega t$ across the two systems, leading to an accurate reproduction of the signals at the other end, provided that a delay compensation technique is implemented.

Asynchronous coupling approach using root mean square (RMS) In this method, instead of employing the $dq0$ transformation, the RMS value of each phase of the three-phase voltages of subsystem 1 along with the system frequency are transmitted to subsystem 2 in the feed-forward path. There, they are transformed back into natural frame signals. $v_a(t) = V_{am}(t) \cos(2\pi f \cdot t)$ represents the voltage of phase a, thus the RMS value is calculated as:

$$V_a^{rms}(t) = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{T_w} \int_{t-T_w}^t v_a(t) \cos(2\pi f \cdot t) dt \quad (3)$$

The reconstruction of the AC voltage signals in Subsystem 2 is achieved through:

$$v_a'(t) = V_a^{rms}(t) \cos(2\pi f' \cdot t) \quad (4)$$

As no voltage angle information is transmitted, a similar procedure for the currents in the feedback path would not make sense. Therefore, the pair of active/reactive power measured at

Figure 22: SISO representation of GD-RTS setup.

subsystem 2 is transferred to subsystem 1. Based on the power measurements, the $dq0$ components of the current are calculated with reference to the measured voltage in subsystem 1, through the following equations:

$$i_d(t) = \frac{3}{2} \frac{P' v_d - Q' v_q}{v_d^2 + v_q^2}, \quad i_q(t) = \frac{3}{2} \frac{P' v_q + Q' v_d}{v_d^2 + v_q^2} \quad (5a,b)$$

Afterwards, first the inverse Clarke transformation is used to obtain the $\alpha\beta\gamma$ components of the current, followed by the inverse Park transformation. The resulting three-phase abc currents are injected to subsystem 1, closing the loop.

4.3.6 Preliminary Investigation of the PHIL Stability

Motivated by the advantages that the delay compensation method brings into the GD-RTS scenario, its applicability in the PHIL scenario was investigated as well. Different approaches were considered such as its application only on the feed-forward path or on both the feed-forward and the feedback path of the V-ITM IA implementation for PHIL simulation. Preliminary results show that delay compensation can effectively improve the accuracy of PHIL setups by eliminating the voltage and current angle differences between the simulated and the hardware systems.

In parallel to the investigation of the applicability of delay compensation, methods that improve the stability of PHIL setups were also reviewed and replicated. More specifically, emphasis was given on the feedback filtering method that is widely used to improve the stability of PHIL setups. However, this comes with the drawback of reducing accuracy, especially during transients by placing a low-pass filter in the feedback path.

Based on the previous findings, future work will focus on the combination of existing methods to propose an advanced IA that improves both the accuracy and the stability properties of PHIL setups.

4.3.7 Results

For the validation of the synchronous and asynchronous coupling methods, a complete stability and accuracy analysis took place. Furthermore, a real-world GD-RTS experiment was conducted between UoS and ICCS-NTUA. Following, the main outcomes of this analysis are presented.

Conventional Stability Analysis and Virtual GD-RTS For the stability analysis, conventional approaches were utilized for modelling and assessment of the GD-RTS setup. The GD-RTS topology was represented as a simplified SISO system, a classical approach that is followed also in PHIL setups. As we have mentioned earlier, the main differences between PHIL and GD-RTS setups are that the latter do not necessarily involve a power amplifier for interfacing of the two subsystems, and that the introduced delays due to the signal exchanges are markedly larger. In Figure 23, the simplified block diagram of the GD-RTS setup is presented. As we can see, stability assessment only considers the delay of the forward path T_d^{ff} , the impedance of subsystem 2, $Z_2(s)$, the delay in the feedback path T_d^{fb} , and the impedance of subsystem 1, $Z_1(s)$. The open-loop transfer function is utilized for the stability analysis of the closed-loop system.

Figure 23: Block diagram of a GD-RTS setup.

$$T_{CL}(s) = e^{-sT_d^{ff}} e^{-sT_d^{fb}} \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)} \quad (6)$$

Eq. 7 allows to adopt the Nyquist stability criterion for the evaluation of GD-RTS setups in which the poles of the closed-loop systems are determined by solving the following equation:

$$1 + \mathbf{T}_{OL}(s) = 0 \quad (7)$$

This means that the studied system will be stable if the Nyquist plot of its open-loop transfer function does not encircle the -1 point. The stability analysis focuses on the evaluation of the impacts of three main factors namely time delay, impedance ratio, and power factor, whose values are given in Table 2. The results are illustrated in Figure 24.

Table 2: Set of parameters used for conventional stability analysis of GD-RTS setups

Scenario	T_d , ms	Z_1/Z_2	PF
Impact of time delay	10, 25, 50, 100, 500	0.9	0.95
Impact of impedance ratio	25	0.95, 1, 1.05	0.95
Impact of power factor	25	0.9	0.85, 0.9, 0.95, 1

(a) Varying time delay with $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.9$ and PF=0.95

(b) Varying impedance ratios with $T_d = 25$ ms and PF=0.95

(c) Varying power factor with $T_d = 25$ ms and $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.9$

Figure 24: Stability analysis of GD-RTS based on SISO conventional analysis and Nyquist criteria.

From the traditional SISO stability analysis with the adopted parameters provided in Table 2, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Time delay (T_d) shows no impact on the stability of GD-RTS setups. With all T_d varies from 10 ms to 500 ms, all the Nyquist plots show the same patterns without any circulation with -1 point (Figure 24a).
- Impedance ratio (Z_1/Z_2) of GD-RTS setups share the same impact with the HIL systems. Those setups with Z_1/Z_2 larger than 1 are unstable demonstrated by the obtained Nyquist plots encircling the point of -1 on the real axis (Figure 24b).
- Power factor of the Hardware under Test (HuT) has an impact on the stability of GD-RTS setups. The increase in PF increases the stability properties of GD-RTS. For instance, with $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.95$ and $T_d = 25$ ms, setups with 0.95 or 1.0 PF HuT are stable while those with lower PF are unstable (Figure 24c).

In order to evaluate the results of the conventional method, various simulations of two GD-RTS setups are conducted in Matlab/Simulink. The results for synchronous dq-based coupling are shown in Figure 25 while those for asynchronous RMS-based coupling are depicted in Figure 26, respectively. The parameters for the simulation scenarios are provided in Table 3.

Table 3: Set of parameters used for various simulation scenarios of GD-RTS setups in Matlab/Simulink

Scenario	T_d , ms	Z_1/Z_2	PF
Impact of time delay	10, 25, 50	0.2	0.95
Impact of impedance ratio	25	0.1, 0.2, 0.3	0.95
Impact of power factor	25	0.2 for dq and 0.25 for RMS	0.75, 0.95

(a) Varying time delay with $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$ and PF=0.95

(b) Varying impedance ratios with $T_d = 25$ ms and PF=0.95

(c) Varying power factor with $T_d = 25$ ms and $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$

Figure 25: Simulation results for synchronous dq-based coupling.

(a) Varying time delay with $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$ and PF=0.95

(b) Varying impedance ratios with $T_d = 25$ ms and PF=0.95

(c) Varying power factor with $T_d = 25$ ms and $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.25$

Figure 26: Simulation results for asynchronous RMS-based coupling.

As of evidence, the two considered coupling types have different stability characteristics and are not in accordance with the theoretical results obtained from conventional SISO stability analysis except for the power factor where the simulation results show a similar pattern. The difference implies that the adopted SISO model defined by (6) cannot cover the influence of the coupling types used for GD-RTS setups. These distinctions are:

- Time delay (T_d): The synchronous dq-based coupling type is more sensitive to the variation of time delay than the asynchronous one. In fact, for $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$ and $PF=0.95$, the former enters instability when the $T_d > 50$ ms (Figure 25a) while the latter still shows a good performance regardless of the increase of T_d up to 125 ms (Figure 26a).
- Impedance ratio (Z_1/Z_2): The distinction can also be seen when considering the variation of impedance ratio. The stability margin concerning this factor for both considered synchronous and asynchronous coupling types are much smaller than the threshold provided by the theoretical SISO analysis. Figure 25b and Figure 26b show that with $T_d=25$ ms and $PF=0.95$, both coupling types become unstable when $Z_1/Z_2 > 0.3$.
- Power Factor (PF): the simulation results show a similar pattern in terms of PF impact with those derived from the conventional method for both coupling types. The decrease in PF reduces the stability boundaries of the GD-RTS setups. As demonstrated in Figure 25c and Figure 26c, for $T_d = 25$ ms and Z_1/Z_2 equal to 0.2 for synchronous coupling and 0.25 for asynchronous coupling, the system moves in unstable region when PF reduces below 0.75.

Accuracy assessment For the complete assessment of the proposed coupling methods, the synchronous and asynchronous, the accuracy of them should be evaluated. For that purpose, the following two metrics are proposed:

- Maximum Instantaneous Power Tracking Error (MIPTTE) is defined as the maximum deviation of the measured apparent power $S'(t)$ of the GD-RTS setup compared to the measured apparent power $S''(t)$ of the full-hardware setup.

$$\text{MIPTTE} = \max \left(\frac{S'(t) - S''(t)}{S'_{RMS}(t)} \right) \quad (8)$$

- Cumulative Power Tracking Error (CPTTE), is defined as the sum of the tracking errors at every time step T_s from the application of disturbance to the time when measured apparent power is restored within the tolerance band, i.e., for period of T_r .

$$\text{CPTTE} = \frac{\sum_{k=0}^N (S'[k] - S''[k])}{S'_{RMS}(t)} \quad (9)$$

where $N = T_{rr}/T_s$. T_s is the time step and T_{rr} is the error restoration time defined as the time span between the initiation of the disturbance up to the time the measured apparent power returns and stabilizes within the defined tolerance band ϵ .

$$T_{rr} = \operatorname{argmin} \{ T_{rr} \in \mathcal{R} \mid \forall t > T_{rr} : \epsilon^+ < S''(t) < \epsilon^- \} \quad (10)$$

The smaller the CPTTE the better is the set point tracking capability.

The defined metrics present a single value that captures the performance of the chosen interface. More specifically, The MIPTTE is a metric for the maximum instantaneous error of a given interface while CPTTE encapsulates its average performance over a given period of time.

(a) MIPTE: T_d vs Z_1/Z_2 , PF = 0.95, for step change in frequency on the left and step change in voltage on the right

(b) CPTE: T_d vs Z_1/Z_2 , PF = 0.95, for step change in frequency on the left and step change in voltage on the right

Figure 27: Accuracy characteristics of synchronous and asynchronous coupling methods for step change in frequency and voltage.

In the following paragraphs some exemplary results from the accuracy analysis are presented. The complete results are presented in the submitted paper which is under review. The accuracy has been evaluated with respect to the same three parameters: time delay, impedance ratio and power factor.

In Figure 27, the results for the accuracy analysis for a step change in frequency (50 Hz to 49 Hz) and RMS voltage value (400 V to 440 V), are presented. The MIPTE and CPTE metrics have been calculated and graphically presented for PF=0.95, while the the range of T_d and Z_1/Z_2 have been chosen such that both coupling methods are stable. More specifically the time delay varies in the range [1ms, 100ms] while the impedance ratio, Z_1/Z_2 in the range [0.05, 0.15]. As it can be seen on the left side of Figure 27, when a step change in frequency occurs, the synchronous coupling exhibits an approximately linear trend and the accuracy deteriorates with increase in T_d or Z_1/Z_2 . The asynchronous coupling exhibits better accuracy performance and it is not affected on the same level when the corresponding parameters are varied. On the other hand, when a step change in RMS value of the voltage occurs, the synchronous coupling presents better accuracy compared to the asynchronous coupling. MIPTE is not affected considerably with increase in T_d , while higher Z_1/Z_2 leads to lower MIPTE. Finally, CIPTE increases with increase in T_d and Z_1/Z_2 .

Practical Implementation As a final step, the applicability of GD-RTS was verified based on an actual experimental setup, in which subsystem 1 was simulated in a Real-time Digital Simulator (RTDS) in the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory (DPSL) at the University of Strathclyde, and subsystem 2 was simulated in a RTDS in Energy Systems Laboratory (EESL) of ICCS-NTUA. The first set of tests were based on the synchronous coupling method. For the communication between the two laboratories apart from the RTDS, a GNET peripheral

card was required, which enables the communication based on commonly used protocols, like User Datagram Protocol (UDP) and Transmission Control Protocol (TCP). Since the faster the communication, the better stability margins are achieved, the UDP protocol was chosen for the experiment, due to its simple, connectionless communication model which is most suitable for time-sensitive applications. After a number of test repetitions, it was proven that the applicability of synchronous coupling method depends on the transmission rate of data exchange between subsystems. It was estimated that a minimum update rate of 2 kHz is required for accurate enough reconstruction of transmitted signals in Subsystems 1 and 2. Currently, an older version of the GTNET card is deployed at EEST which limits the update rate to to 100 Hz. A newer version, the GTNETx2 card, is installed at the DPSL laboratory and enables up to 5 kHz update rate, depending on the maximum number of messages and the data to be transmitted. Due to this hardware limitation, the next set of tests were based on the asynchronous coupling method, which was proven to be a suitable method to overcome limitations related to the limited transmission rate.

As it can be seen in Figure 28, the average time delay between DPSL in Scotland and EESL in Greece, has been measured to around 60 ms. In the bottom of the same figure, the results for a case study are presented in which a PF of 1 has been chosen while varying the impedance ratios (Z_1/Z_2). The data transmission rate for the reported results is 100 Hz. As it can be seen from the figure, the experimental results are in compliance with the stability boundaries determined in the context of Track 2.4. The advanced stability analysis, showcased in Figure 48, confirms the applicability and sufficiency of the developed mathematical modelling.

Results from the investigation of existing and advanced IAs for PHIL setups will be presented in the following deliverable.

4.3.8 Further Work

Further work will focus on the investigation of advanced IAs algorithms, such as the ones already investigated in the GD-RTS scenario, to PHIL simulation setups, where different amount

Figure 28: Real-world asynchronous GD-RTS results

of delays and components are under consideration. In fact, emphasis will be given on the combination of different methods that improve the stability and the accuracy of PHIL simulations, thus improving their applicability in the process of validating modern power and energy systems.

4.4 Sensitivity Analysis based on Mathematical Modelling of PHIL Simulation Systems

4.4.1 Motivation

Real-time simulation has become part of the everyday practice for electric power engineers in the last few years. Upcoming challenges in electric power grids require suitable and applicable testing methods. HIL simulation systems represent an advanced methodology for testing and investigating such kind of electric power grids.

4.4.2 Problem Statement

In HIL simulation systems, often dynamic analysis is related to stability property assessment and signal accuracy analysis. In this work, we address the identification of suitable methods to analyse the sensitivity properties of HIL simulation systems with different applied PHIL interface topologies. Similarly to already existent frameworks for stability and accuracy analysis, a framework for sensitivity analysis is intended to be created and validated with the help of experimental HIL test setups.

Sensitivity in control systems is a measure of change in system response with regard to the change in input or any other parameter of the systems. In control systems, the sensitivity of a system is mainly studied with respect to a parameter variation. In the following equation, the sensitivity of system "S" with transfer function "T" with respect to the parameter "K" and the indication of disturbances "δ" related to signals and parameters is described:

$$S_K^T = \frac{K}{T} \cdot \frac{\delta T}{\delta K} \quad (11)$$

4.4.3 Scope

The scope of this activity has been defined through the formulation of objectives for three consecutive sprints: Sprints 1, 2, and 3. The development time related to these sprints is divided into three parts:

- *Sprint 1*: Review and modelling principles for HIL.
- *Sprint 2*: Validation of analytical modelling principles for sensitivity.
- *Sprint 3*: Framework for sensitivity analysis.

4.4.4 Approach

In Section 4.4.4, the modelling principles for the sensitivity analysis are elaborated. Based on these fundamental principles, the sensitivity analysis for HIL simulation systems is introduced. As an introduction, an overview over HIL simulation methodologies which are relevant for this work is given. Generally, real-time computing platforms are widely used for manifold simulation techniques. Co-Simulation and CHIL simulation are methods gaining increasing importance in rapid prototyping, system pre-compliance testing, or multi-domain system validation.

Figure 29 shows the basic difference between PHIL and CHIL simulations in a graphical way. It mainly consists of the integration of the PHIL interface which includes the amplification unit and the signal measurement. However, this structural differential implies a huge impact from a system theory point of view. The CHIL method is a real-time capable method mainly used for rapid prototyping and the specific verification of digital controllers. It combines many advantages of hardware testing methods and software simulation methods. The basic idea is comprised that a specific control board runs on its target platform, while it is tested versus a simulated model of the embedded system. A standard execution platform is given in an industrial PC, embedded controller, remote terminal unit, programmable logic controller, or intelligent end service.

Figure 29: Topology of CHIL and PHIL simulation systems.

The following simulation methodologies have to be distinguished depending on their specific realisation (Andrn, Lehfu, & Strasser, 2013):

- *Controller hardware-in-the-loop (CHIL)*: A simulation of an electric power system is operated by means of a a PC-based hardware or by an RTS, while the controller execution runs on its own target platform in real-time.
- *Software-in-the-loop (SIL)*: The simulation of the electric power system and simulation of the controller are both executed on the same PC or the RTS. The SIL method is an offline simulation method, however, real-time execution is possible.
- *Co-Simulation*: The simulation of an electric power system and the simulation of the controller are executed on different PCs or RTS devices. The Co-simulation method is an offline simulation method, however, real-time execution is possible.

For CHIL simulation setups, the peripherals of the simulation system are simulated in a real-time software environment which is connected to a control board. It does not make any difference for the controller whether it is integrated in an offline simulation running on the same hardware or whether it is integrated in the real process. For SIL systems, the controller and the peripheral system environment are simulated on the same PC-based hardware platform. The controller is developed as a software emulation of the electric power system or an arbitrary multi-domain system. Even if both processes run on the same hardware, the data exchange between both simulation environments is existent or emulated (shared memory, an Ethernet-based TCP/IP, or a UDP/IP communication). However, any kind of communication time delays have to be considered for this type of simulation. In this case, the SIL method can be categorised as an offline real-time concept. Co-simulation provides the possibility to perform a simulation on one PC or on the RTS between peripheral system domains (i.e., electric, mechanic, thermal, hydraulic), and to run the control application execution on a separated PC-based hardware. The control application can be tested in an independent, distributed environment and even the final communication protocol can be used. Hereby, a valid emulation of the communication interface is commonly implemented and set up on the Co-simulation platform. Such a communication emulator between controller and the power system is often used as a validation of the controller and is commonly known under the term emulated real-time communication.

Figure 30 explains the real-time conditions applied for CHIL and PHIL simulations. In case of real-time (a), the execution time τ_e for the simulation of the system is shorter or equal to the selected time step. The simulation is considered to be real-time or online. In case of non-real-time (b), the execution time τ_e is longer than its time step size for one or more time steps. Simulation overruns occur in this case and the simulation is classified as non-real-time or offline. All real-time simulators are obliged to the run-time criterion stated in the first case (a). The second case is representative for most typical offline programs, emulators, or calculators showing no real-time capability (b). Either the system model has to be simplified to reduce the computation time, or the time step has to be increased adequately to run it in real-time.

PHIL simulation systems consist of multiple blocks representing structural areas connected one to each other via interacting signals, in principle. The basic structure of the PHIL simulation technique is characterised by the causal signal flow and does not differentiate initially between high and low power scale. Three major parts are characteristic for PHIL simulation systems and given as (Lauss et al., 2015):

- *The software part:* The dominant component of the software side is constituted by the real-time system (RTS) calculating the simulated models in real-time. Its task is clearly defined as it must maintain the guaranteed real-time capability at all times, collect the incoming signals, and process the outgoing signals in the given, well-defined time step. The link to the interface primarily consists of the I/O ports transferring in and outgoing signals within the running PHIL simulation.
- *The PHIL interface:* The primary task of the PHIL interface or also known as the power interface (PI) is comprised in the bidirectional, self-contained link from the software to the hardware part, and the suitable, intended interface algorithms (IA) that is inherently interlinked to the power amplification unit. The key hardware component of the PHIL interface is the PA featuring specific signal bandwidths, delay times, power and protection limits. The PHIL interface contains both forward and backward signal paths with I/O ports, conditioning circuits, interface algorithms, and signal measurement devices.
- *The hardware part:* This part can consist of simple passive components, standard testing

Figure 30: Definition of real-time (a) and non-real-time simulation (b).

equipment, or custom devices. It can be assembled out of various passive or active components for particular subsystems or even out of entire systems. It represents the target of the simulation and has to exist in physical hardware being inherently connected to the PHIL interface. The link to the PHIL interface is stated via dedicated signal measurement paths in the feedback loop and the power connection in the feed-forward loop.

From a system point of view, a PHIL simulation system represents nonlinear control system with time-discrete and time continuous parts on the software and the hardware side, respectively. In digital HIL simulation systems, the calculation of the RTS produces a set of results at every given time step. These signals are transferred to the hardware part through the PHIL interface. In the hardware part, time continuous signals are existent for the power network what includes power amplification units as electric sources and hardware devices as Hardware under Investigation (Hul). A measured set of signals represents time-continuous feedback signals which are used as an input of the time discrete software part representing the Model under Investigation (Mul). Since the majority of real-time computing systems are of discrete and not analogous nature, this statement is valid for modern PHIL simulation (Faruque & Dinavahi, 2009).

In principle, system instability is a failure condition for PHIL simulation and has to be avoided at all times. Analytic measures based on modelling principles are used to estimate the limits of stability, as presented in the following. Each PHIL simulation demands a certain level of accuracy. Otherwise, results will be meaningless. Therefore, it is necessary to achieve high accuracy with implemented PHIL interfaces and given Hul devices. When the availability of a model for the Hul is not given in detail, system analysis is even more difficult and model approximations of the Hul have to be found. In general, stability is an imperative criterion for the safety of equipment. It represents a pre-condition for the determination of the simulation accuracy and of the sensitivity. Hardware devices such as the PA or the Hul may get damaged in case of instability. Therefore, appropriate countermeasures should be implemented to detect unstable operation and return to a safe state.

In analogy to stability and accuracy analysis, the sensitivity analysis represents a key criterion for PHIL simulation. In general, the sensitivity of the PHIL setup is characterised by issues such as topological properties of the PHIL interface (current/voltage-type topology, interface algorithms), dynamics of the measurement device, or the power amplifying stage. In the control theory context, this problem could be compared to achieve a high robust control system, but at the same time not making compromises on the accuracy performance of the applied interface. In addition, the inherent time delay within the PHIL simulation caused by technological or topological reasons is decisive for the nonlinear system behaviour. It affects stability, accuracy, and sensitivity properties at the same time, therefore, careful pre-analysis of the studied HIL setup is required.

In Figure 31, a basic PHIL setup is depicted and represents the reference circuit for subsequent fundamental statements and following considerations. The system of interest (Sul) is the complete real-world system decomposed into Hul and model of interest (Mul), as depicted in (a). When analysed via HIL, the generalised Sul for CHIL and PHIL simulation is shown in (b).

Figure 31: Basic architecture of (a) the Sul and (b) the corresponding PHIL simulation system.

The aforementioned hybrid system structure states that the theoretical methods, as described in control literature (Dorf & Bishop, 2011), (Sastry, 2013) for hybrid systems, may be used to analyse PHIL systems for stability in the case of a linear Hul. For example, a discrete time equivalent description of a PHIL simulation of a series connection of resistor and inductance is given in (Ayasun, Fischl, Vallieu, Braun, & Cadırlı, 2007), and parameter regions of the components in which the simulation runs stable are found from a straightforward analysis.

In what follows, the continuous time approach is applied for the modelling of respective PHIL

simulation systems. The definition of the following criteria are applicable to PHIL simulation systems and may serve as modelling principles for the sensitivity analysis:

- The simulation system or Mul represents the portion of the Sul modeled and instantiated in software on an RTS. The Mul interacts with the Hul through HIL interfaces. For the purpose of system analysis, the Mul is considered as time-continuous and a transfer function representation can be applied.
- Based on the discrete time nature of the RTS, a corresponding time delay of one time step size τ_S is introduced as an adequate substitution of the execution time and the resulting idle time for time-continuous system analysis (Hong et al., 2010) (Ren, 2007).

Based on this approach, the identification of the elementary transfer functions of the PHIL simulation is important for the assessment of the open-loop and closed-loop transfer function allowing valid statements on the dynamics of the PHIL system. Definitions related to real-time systems and corresponding transfer function representations, as introduced above, sets the foundation for basic principles for the sensitivity analysis of HIL simulation systems.

4.4.5 Implementation

In a first step, a definition of sensitivity for basic closed-loop systems has to be found and defined. Valuable contributions for subsequent works of the sensitivity analysis can be found in literature (Ren, 2007), (Astrom & Murray, 2010), (Yepes, Freijedo, Lopez, & Doval-Gandoy, 2011). In a next step, sensitivity analysis has to be defined for the particular case of HIL simulation systems. In a further step, results from analytical sensitivity evaluations and experimental test setups should be compared for the purpose of validation. Finally, the validation methodology should be described in correct way so that results from model analysis and experimental setups can be compared in a validated and reproducible way.

In Figure 32, the block diagram of a basic feedback system is shown (Astrom & Murray, 2010). It is assumed that the system is linear. The system loop is composed of two components: the process $P(s)$, and the controller. The controller consists of the feedforward block $F(s)$ and the feedback block $C(s)$. For system analysis, the reference input signal r , the process output signal η , and the measured output signal y are defined. In addition, two disturbances acting as signals on the process are defined: the load disturbance d and the measurement noise n .

Figure 32: Block diagram of a basic feedback loop.

For this system and assuming $F(s) = 0$, the closed-loop system transfer function is given by:

$$G_{yr}(s) = \frac{P(s)C(s)}{1 + P(s)C(s)} \quad (12)$$

Considering the three external signals r , d , n and the output signals η , y , u , these relations can be expressed in terms as matrix expression, as shown in figure 32. For HIL systems, the special case when $F(s) = 1$ is called a system with pure error feedback. In this case, all control actions are based on feedback from the error only and the system is completely characterized by four transfer functions: the sensitivity function $S(s)$, the complementary sensitivity function $T(s)$, the load sensitivity function $PS(s)$, and the noise sensitivity function $CS(s)$. According to (Astrom & Murray, 2010), the transfer function representations can be derived to:

$$S(s) = \frac{1}{1 + P(s)C(s)} \quad (13)$$

$$T(s) = \frac{P(s)C(s)}{1 + P(s)C(s)} \quad (14)$$

$$PS(s) = \frac{P(s)}{1 + P(s)C(s)} \quad (15)$$

$$CS(s) = \frac{C(s)}{1 + P(s)C(s)} \quad (16)$$

In general, the block diagram of this basic feedback loop system shows the same structure, corresponding input and output signals, and possible disturbances as for comparable, real-time based closed-loop HIL simulation systems, as introduced in Figure 31, Section 4.4.4. The transfer functions (13)-(16) describe the effect of the signals r , d and n on the outputs η , y and u , characterising the sensitivity of the system with respect to external inputs. For example, the sensitivity function $S(s)$ in (13) corresponds to the transfer function between n and y and quantifies the sensitivity of the system output with respect to a disturbance placed after the process P . Similarly, the complementary sensitivity function $T(s)$ in (14) corresponds to the transfer function (with changed sign) between d and u and quantifies the sensitivity of the controller output with respect to a disturbance placed before the process P .

Based on the principles for HIL systems, the block diagram for closed-loop HIL simulation systems is discussed. Figure 33 shows the block diagram of a PHIL simulation system with generic power interface. Software system S_1 and hardware system S_2 are interconnected via a dedicated power interface PI.

In general, the system S_1 can always be represented as a Thévenin equivalent of the network model (Dorf & Bishop, 2011) and consists of a voltage source with the voltage U_S and impedance Z_1 . The Thévenin's theorem and its dual, the Norton's theorem, are commonly used to simplify network models and applied for analysis of HIL simulation systems. In case of voltage-type HIL or power interfaces, the Thévenin equivalent is commonly applied, in case of a current-type interfacing, the Norton equivalent may be used preferably. Likewise, for hardware system S_2 the Thévenin or Norton equivalent is applied, respectively.

The terminals of the software system S_1 show interface signals U_D and I_D , where the subscript "D" is used for "digital". For the hardware system S_2 , the interface signal are U_A and I_A and the subscript "A" is used for "analog", since the hardware system consists of hardware-only components.

Figure 33: Block diagram of a PHIL simulation system with generic power interface.

All HIL simulation systems are hybrid systems consisting of software systems and hardware systems, in general. Interfaces are designed and used for the interconnection of respective hardware and software systems. Since one of the principal requirements for HIL simulation is that the software systems must be run and executed in real-time, the time step size of the software system is of fundamental relevance. By definition, the execution time τ_e may never exceed the time step size τ_S for real-time systems. Otherwise, the system is non real time or offline. As shown in literature (Ayasun et al., 2007), (Faruque, Strasser, Lauss, Jalili-Marandi, et al., 2015), (Lauss et al., 2015), the time step size τ_S is the fixed duration which is used for model representation of the software system executed in real-time. For the purpose of modelling, the delay time τ_d is defined as: $\tau_d \leq \tau_S$.

Figure 34 shows the model representation of a PHIL simulation system with an Ideal Transformer Model (ITM) voltage-type power interface. When using time-continuous modelling, as proposed in Section 4.4.4, the sampling of the real-time simulator and the time needed to transmit its output to the power interface can be modelled as a delay τ_S and represented in the Laplace domain as the exponential transfer function:

$$T_S(s) = e^{-s\tau_S} \quad (17)$$

Note that the delay associated to the interactions between the real-time simulator and the power interface affects the forward and the feedback path in the same way, motivating the inclusion of the transfer function $T_S(s)$ in both directions of the communication channel. For PHIL systems as shown in Figure 34, the overall delay τ_d caused by the discrete computation of real-time can be formulated as follows:

$$T_d(s) = e^{-s2\tau_S} \quad (18)$$

In above equation, the term " $e^{-s\tau_S}$ " indicates the corresponding delay time related to one, single time step size related to the discrete operation of the real-time simulator.

In Figure 34, further transfer functions are highlighted which are of relevance for a proper model representation of a PHIL simulation system. In the forward path, the transfer functions $T_{FW}(s)$ and $T_{AM}(s)$ contain the dynamic behaviour of signal processing or filtering blocks and the amplification unit, respectively. For the feedback path, the transfer functions $T_M(s)$ and $T_{FB}(s)$ are considered representing the dynamic behaviour of signal measurement devices and signal processing or filtering blocks, respectively. For stability, accuracy, and also sensitivity analysis, these transfer functions integrated into the closed-loop system have to be identified or calculated. Examples and guidelines on the capturing of these important transfer functions can be found in literature (Ayasun et al., 2007), (de Jong et al., 2012), (Langston, Schoder, Steurer, Edrington, & Roberts, 2018) and many others.

Figure 34: Model representation of a voltage-type power interface integrated in a PHIL system.

Figure 35: Block diagram of a voltage-type power interface integrated in a PHIL system.

Figure 35 introduces the corresponding block diagram based on the model representation of Figure 34. As can be seen in the bottom of Figure 35, the block diagram of all components integrated into an ITM voltage-type PHIL simulation are composed as a closed-loop feedback system. This block diagram representation may be used for further developing the framework for sensitivity analysis. Of course, when other interfacing techniques or methodologies used, the block diagram must be modified accordingly. In this specific example of PHIL with ITM interface, the impedance $Z_1(s)$ has been placed in the feedback loop, disturbances on the voltage U_D and on the currents I_A and I_D have been considered, and the transfer functions C

and P have been defined as:

$$C(s) = e^{-2\tau_s} T_{FW}(s) T_{AM}(s) \frac{1}{Z_2(s)} \quad (19)$$

$$P(s) = T_M(s) T_{FB}(s) e^{-2\tau_s} \quad (20)$$

Based on above-mentioned findings, the sensitivity for PHIL simulation systems can be assessed by computing the sensitivity functions, in general, introduced in (13) - (16). In particular, the sensitivity transfer function is given by:

$$S(s) = W_{I_D, \delta I_d} = \frac{1}{1 + Z_1(s)P(s)C(s)} \quad (21)$$

and can be interpreted as the transfer function between δI_d and I_d , characterising the sensitivity between the output current of the digital interface and the associated disturbance. With the same approach, the other relevant transfer functions can be defined as:

$$T(s) = -W_{U_D, \delta U_d} = \frac{Z_1(s)P(s)C(s)}{1 + Z_1(s)P(s)C(s)} \quad (22)$$

$$PS(s) = W_{I_D, \delta I_A} = \frac{P(s)}{1 + Z_1(s)P(s)C(s)} \quad (23)$$

$$CS(s) = W_{I_A, \delta U_d} = \frac{C(s)}{1 + Z_1(s)P(s)C(s)} \quad (24)$$

Sensitivity analysis can now be performed by finding corresponding transfer functions for equations (21)-(24) with respect to implemented interface methodologies such as the voltage or current-type ITM, PCD, DIM, TFA method, respectively. Block diagrams of model representations can be found numerously in state-of-the-art literature and can be used for sensitivity analysis. The open-loop transfer function of the PHIL system in Figure 36 is given by:

$$F_O(s) = \underbrace{e^{-s\tau_s} T_{FW}(s) T_{AM}(s)}_{C(s)} \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)} \underbrace{e^{-s\tau_s} T_{FB}(s) T_M(s)}_{P(s)} \quad (25)$$

where $T_{FW}(s)$, $T_{FB}(s)$ represent the signal processing unit in the feed-forward and feed-back path respectively, $T_{AM}(s)$ represents the voltage-type power amplifier, $T_M(s)$ represents the current measurement unit. The closed-loop transfer functions representing the relationship between the outputs (i.e., U_D , U_A , I_A , I_D) and the equivalent voltage signal (V_S) are:

$$F_{cl} = \begin{cases} \frac{U_D(s)}{U_S(s)} = \frac{1}{1+F_O(s)} \\ \frac{U_A(s)}{U_S(s)} = \frac{C(s)}{1+F_O(s)} \\ \frac{I_A(s)}{U_S(s)} = \frac{C(s)/Z_2(s)}{1+F_O(s)} \\ \frac{I_D(s)}{U_S(s)} = \frac{C(s)P(s)/Z_2(s)}{1+F_O(s)} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

Figure 36: Block diagram of a voltage-type ITM power interface integrated in a PHIL system.

Figure 37: Block diagram of a voltage-type ITM power interface integrated in a PHIL system.

Figure 37 presents the PHIL system block diagram with external disturbances. Sensitivity function $S(s)$, a transfer function from the output to its associated disturbance (δU or δI) at each stage, is employed to assess the system sensitivity to such a disturbance (i.e., output disturbance) and is given by:

$$S(s) = \begin{cases} W_{U_D, \delta U_D} = \frac{U_D(s)}{\delta U_D(s)} = \frac{1}{1+F_O(s)} \\ W_{U_A, \delta U_A} = \frac{U_A(s)}{\delta U_A(s)} = \frac{1}{1+F_O(s)} \\ W_{I_A, \delta I_A} = \frac{I_A(s)}{\delta I_A(s)} = \frac{1}{1+F_O(s)} \\ W_{I_D, \delta I_D} = \frac{I_D(s)}{\delta I_D(s)} = \frac{1}{1+F_O(s)} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

Sensitivity functions $S_i(s)$, transfer functions from the system output to all the external distur-

bances (δU and δI), are employed to assess the system sensitivity to such a disturbance. Note that, the voltage signal U_A to be fed to the power hardware is the signal of interest and is utilised for the following analysis. The sensitivity functions $\mathbf{S}_i(s)$ are defined as:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{S}(s) = W_{U_A, \delta U_A} = \frac{U_A(s)}{\delta U_A(s)} = \frac{1}{1+TF_{ol}} \\ \mathbf{S}_1(s) = W_{U_A, \delta U_D} = \frac{U_A(s)}{\delta U_D(s)} = \frac{C(s)}{1+TF_{ol}} \\ \mathbf{S}_2(s) = W_{U_A, \delta I_D} = \frac{U_A(s)}{\delta I_D(s)} = \frac{-C(s)Z_1(s)}{1+TF_{ol}} \\ \mathbf{S}_3(s) = W_{U_A, \delta I_A} = \frac{U_A(s)}{\delta I_A(s)} = \frac{-C(s)P(s)Z_1(s)}{1+TF_{ol}} \end{cases} \quad (28)$$

For the external disturbance with frequency w , the magnitude (i.e., $|\mathbf{S}(jw)|$) of the sensitivity function determines the extent to which the external disturbance distorts the output signal and deteriorates the simulation accuracy. It is obvious that the output disturbance signal with frequency w such that $|\mathbf{S}(jw)|$ is greater than 1 is amplified, otherwise is attenuated within the feedback loop.

$$|\mathbf{S}(jw)| = \left| \frac{1}{1 + C(jw)P(jw) \frac{Z_1(jw)}{Z_2(jw)}} \right| \quad (29)$$

The Vector Margin (VM) is defined as the shortest distance from the Nyquist curve of the open-loop transfer function TF_{ol} to the critical point $(-1,0)$ in the real-axis.

$$VM = |1 + TF_{ol}(jw_0)|_{min} = \left| 1 + C(jw_0)P(jw_0) \frac{Z_1(jw_0)}{Z_2(jw_0)} \right|_{min} \quad (30)$$

As shown in Figure 38, the shortest distance between Nyquist curve and the critical point $(-1,0)$ is achieved at the point with frequency w_0 , at which the magnitude of the sensitivity function is at its maximum value. The VM is the inverse of the maximum magnitude of the sensitivity function. Note that the smaller the VM (i.e., a greater $|\mathbf{S}(jw)|_{max}$) is, the closer the Nyquist plot to the critical point $(-1,0)$ is. The overall closed-loop system is closer to unstable state. The magnitude of the sensitivity function (i.e., $|\mathbf{S}(jw)|_{max}$) indicates the degree of overall PHIL stability.

$$|\mathbf{S}(jw)|_{max} = \left| \frac{1}{1 + C(jw_0)P(jw_0) \frac{Z_1(jw_0)}{Z_2(jw_0)}} \right|_{max} \quad (31)$$

$$VM = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{S}(jw)|_{max}}, w = w_0 \quad (32)$$

Figure 38 illustrates the relationship between the Gain Margin (GM), Phase Margin (PM), and VM, whose relationship can be derived from the following inequalities:

$$\begin{cases} VM + \frac{1}{GM} \leq 1 \\ VM \leq \sin(\text{PM}) \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

Figure 38: Nyquist diagram of the open-loop transfer function and stability margins.

Substituting (32) into (33), relations between the sensitivity function and stability margins are given by:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{1}{|S(jw)|} \leq \frac{GM-1}{GM} \quad \forall w > 0 \\ \frac{1}{|S(jw)|} \leq \sin(\text{PM}) \quad \forall w > 0 \end{array} \right. \quad (34)$$

The validation of analytical and experimental results could be performed successfully using simulation PHIL test setups and real-world PHIL laboratory setups. The full results can be found in (Lauss et al., 2022). In that publication, Section IV contains an analytical assessment of the sensitivity framework using theoretic evaluations on PHIL system models. In Section V, in-detail discussions related to the experimental assessment and the validation process based on a comparison between results derived from PHIL simulation setups and hardware-only tests are elaborated for the sensitivity framework. Similar to this document, the manuscript is a joint effort with the team responsible for Track 2.3 as well.

4.4.6 Results

As results of this activity, the objectives of Sprints 1, 2, and 3 have been successfully achieved and all tasks could be finalised. In what follows, major conclusions based on research activities in respective sprints are summarised:

- *Sprint 1*: In a first step, a thorough literature review has been performed and results have been listed in a well-arranged table representation. Here, important ratings of IA are highlighted and brief summaries of each publication is given.

In a second step, fundamental principles for the modelling process are defined and applied for real-time based PHIL simulation systems. This includes the differentiation between CHIL and PHIL systems as well as applied real-time and non-real-time constraints.

- *Sprint 2:* In a third step, the modelling focused on the in-depth representation of power interfaces and related IAs for PHIL systems. Transfer function representations, block diagrams, and signal disturbances are identified for open-loop and closed-loop systems.

In a further step, criteria for system stability or accuracy are discussed and based on this concept, system properties and related measures such as the phase margin, the gain margin, or the vector margin are introduced. The developed framework facilitated to pre-determine or to estimate dynamic properties with respect to robustness and sensitivity of investigated PHIL systems in an analytical way.

In a next step, selected case studies represent the basis for the validation process. On the one side, some case studies are purely analytical models representing *simulated PHIL setups*, and on the other side other case studies are implemented by means of *experimental PHIL setups*. Using results of both types of case studies, the validation process of the framework for sensitivity analysis could be performed by comparing either analytical or experimental results with developed metrics of the sensitivity framework. Results confirm that the validation process has been successfully performed for different types of PHIL systems.

- *Sprint 3:* In a final step and as a resulting work effort, the team of the real-time simulation activity made a joint effort and submitted a journal paper (Lauss et al., 2022). This manuscript helps every PHIL user to evaluate system properties of PHIL systems with respect to stability, accuracy, and in particular to the generalised sensitivity behaviour.

4.4.7 Further work

As related to this track “Sensitivity analysis based on mathematical modelling”, close collaboration with Track 2.2 “Improving stability of HIL simulation” is targeted and intended at a later stage. During Sprints 2 and 3, experimental validation of sensitivity analysis may be applied for advanced PHIL interface topologies, wherever applicable. Therefore, additional works may be suitable and applicable for the demonstration activity of the project.

4.5 Applicability of Different RT Methods for Validation

4.5.1 Motivation

In the last decades, RT simulations have been widely adopted not only in academia but also in the industry for validating new technologies or testing new equipment (Pokharel & Ho, 2020; Alenius et al., 2020; Lucia et al., 2010; Upamanyu & Narayanan, 2019). The most popular method has been HIL which can be performed as CHIL or PHIL. These methods consist of a DRTS connected to controllers (for CHIL) or power hardware (for PHIL) and typically take place in a single RI.

However, advanced solutions/technologies, especially in modern cyber-physical power and energy systems, require new validation methods with the incorporation of more DRTS and equipment. This presents many challenges to a single RI with limited experimental capabilities. Consequently, GD-RTS have appeared as an alternative method with several advantages. As

the name suggests, GD-RTS provides a solution for splitting experiments into various subsystems which can be located across geographically distributed RIs. This has indeed brought many more testing capabilities.

Similar to HIL simulations, stability and accuracy are the critical factors for the applicability of GD-RTS. Nevertheless, unlike conventional HIL setups, GD-RTS experiments are spread over large geographical distances and their split subsystems are interconnected over the Internet, resulting in larger time delays and packet losses. Therefore, the objective of Track 2.4 is to investigate the stability of different types of GD-RTS coupling methods to determine their applicability in terms of stability.

4.5.2 Problem Statement

The selection of HIL setups for a test largely depends upon their stability and accuracy assessment. Amongst impacting factors, time delays and interface algorithms are of the highest importance (Pokharel & Ho, 2020; Upamanyu & Narayanan, 2019). In HIL applications, time delays are mostly caused by the signal amplification in power amplifiers and the simulation time steps in DRTS. The delay in data transmission between DRTS and the HuT is, usually, negligible. Sharing a similar HIL structure, the performance of any GD-RTS setup is driven by its stability and accuracy properties. However, in GD-RTS setups, the signal exchange between DRTS and HuT must take place over the Internet, and thus delay in data transmission plays a much more significant impact. As a result, different coupling types should be deployed upon the required dynamics of the test to convert the exchanged signals in DC quantities to achieve stability. The adoption of these new coupling types renders the conventional stability analysis methods irrelevant and thus their applicability should be investigated by using appropriate assessment approaches.

4.5.3 Scope

The scope of the track covers the following two activities:

- Developing models for stability analysis of synchronous dq-based (Figure 39a) and asynchronous RMS-based (Figure 39b) coupling types dedicated for GD-RTS setups.
- Establishing the stability boundaries for the selection coupling types for GD-RTS setups with regards to different impacting factors, including impedance ratio between equivalent impedance of simulated network (Z_1) and that of HuT (Z_2), i.e. Z_1/Z_2 , time delay (T_d), and HuT power factor (PF).

4.5.4 Approach

Firstly, the limitations of the conventional SISO stability analysis methods, which have been widely using for HIL setups, are identified by comparing its evaluation results with the simulation results. Then, new small-signal-based (Multiple Inputs, Multiple Outputs (MIMO)) stability models for the stability analysis dedicated to synchronous dq-based and asynchronous RMS-based coupling interfaces are developed. The theoretical results obtained from proposed models are validated by means of simulation in the Matlab/Simulink environment. A practical setup for asynchronous coupling has been also conducted to confirm the theoretical and simulation results.

Figure 39: Overview of GD-RTS setups with different coupling types

4.5.5 Implementation

According to the traditional approach, the stability of GD-RTS setups can be evaluated by using the open-loop transfer function defined by (Upamanyu & Narayanan, 2019; Pokharel & Ho, 2020).

$$\mathbf{T}_{OL}(s) = \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)} e^{-s2T_d} \quad (35)$$

where $Z_1(s)$ and $Z_2(s)$ are the impedances of Subsystem 1 and Subsystem 2, respectively in Figure 27, and $2T_d$ is the overall time delay of the overall setups with an assumption that both time delays of the feed forward and feedback circuits are equal to T_d .

As was presented in Track 2.2, the simplified consideration of the closed-loop system for the stability analysis does not provide accurate results regarding the impact of coupling method to be incorporated. For that reason, in the frame of Track 2.4 an advanced stability analysis is introduced, which provides considerable accurate results that completely match the simulation and experimental observations.

The block diagram for the derivation of the open-loop MIMO transfer function of the synchronous dq-based coupling is illustrated in Figure 40. It is noted that the PLL block makes the dynamics of v_{dq} and θ_v coupled and nonlinear. Decoupling and linearizing the dynamics can be achieved by representing $\hat{\theta}_v(s)$ by $\hat{v}_q(s)$ as following (Pokharel & Ho, 2020):

$$\hat{\theta}_v(s) = \frac{G_{PLL}(s)}{1 + \bar{V}_d G_{PLL}(s)} \hat{v}_q(s) = T_{PLL}(s) \hat{v}_q(s) \quad (36)$$

Figure 40: Block diagram of synchronous dq-based GD-RTS implementation in s-domain.

where $G_{PLL}(s)$ and $T_{PLL}(s)$ are defined by

$$G_{PLL}(s) = \left(k_p + \frac{k_i}{s} \right) \frac{1}{s} \quad (37)$$

$$T_{PLL}(s) = \frac{G_{PLL}(s)}{1 + \bar{V}_d G_{PLL}(s)} \quad (38)$$

where k_i and k_d are integral and proportional coefficients of the PLL block.

Then, by applying the small-signal stability principle for the transformation of voltage signals in the feedback loop, i.e. v_{abc} in Figure 40, one can obtain the MIMO transfer function in s-domain of the forward path as

$$\mathbf{T}_{ff-dq}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-sT_d} + \bar{V}_d T_{PLL} & \bar{V}_d e^{-sT_d} T_{PLL} \\ 0 & e^{-sT_d} + \bar{V}_d T_{PLL} - \bar{V}_d T_{PLL} e^{-sT_d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Similarly, the use of the same procedure for the feedback path yields

$$\mathbf{T}_{fb-dq}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} e^{-sT_d} + \bar{I}_d T_{PLL} & \bar{I}_d e^{-sT_d} T_{PLL} \\ 0 & e^{-sT_d} + \bar{I}_d T_{PLL} - \bar{I}_d T_{PLL} e^{-sT_d} \end{bmatrix} \quad (40)$$

Finally, the overall MIMO open-loop transfer function for the synchronous dq-based GD-RTS setup can be written by

$$\mathbf{T}_{OL-dq}(s) = \mathbf{T}_{ff-dq}(s) \cdot \mathbf{T}_{fb-dq}(s) \cdot \frac{Z_1(s)}{Z_2(s)} \quad (41)$$

The stability analysis of the synchronous dq-based coupling type by using the derived model, i.e. (41), with the similar set of parameter provided in Table 3, is illustrated in Figure 41 for varying time delay, in Figure 42 for varying impedance ratio, and lastly in Figure 43 for varying power factor.

(a) $T_d = 10$ ms

(b) $T_d = 25$ ms

(c) $T_d = 50$ ms

Figure 41: Nyquist plots of dq-based coupling for varying time delay with $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$ and $PF=0.95$

(a) $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.1$

(b) $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$

(c) $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.3$

Figure 42: Nyquist plots of dq-based coupling for varying impedance ratio with $T_d = 25$ ms and $PF=0.95$

(a) PF = 1.0

(b) PF = 0.95

(c) PF = 0.75

Figure 43: Nyquist plots of dq-based coupling for varying PF with $T_d = 25\text{ ms}$ and $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$

Figure 44: Block diagram of asynchronous RMS-based GD-RTS implementation in s -domain.

The block diagram for the derivation of the open-loop MIMO transfer function of asynchronous RMS-based coupling is illustrated in Figure 44. Similarly, by applying the small-signal stability principle the overall open-loop transfer function of this system can be defined by

$$\mathbf{T}_{OL-rms}(s) = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2e^{-sT_d}}{3\bar{V}_d} \left[\bar{I}_d \frac{\bar{V}_d}{Z_2(s)} \right] (-T_1 + 2T_2) + \bar{I}_d T_{PLL} Z_2(s) & 0 \\ 0 & \bar{I}_d T_{PLL} Z_2(s) \end{bmatrix} \quad (42)$$

where

$$T_1(s) = e^{-sT_d} \bar{V}_d T_{PLL} \quad (43)$$

$$T_2(s) = e^{-sT_d} \frac{1 - e^{-sT_w}}{\sqrt{2}T_w} \frac{s}{s^2 + \omega_0^2} \quad (44)$$

and T_w is the RMS window length.

The stability analysis of the asynchronous RMS-based coupling type by using the developed model, i.e. (42), with the similar set of parameter provided in Table 3 is illustrated in Figure 45 for varying time delay, Figure 46 for varying impedance ratio, and lastly Figure 47 for varying power factor.

(a) $T_d = 25$ ms

(b) $T_d = 50$ ms

(c) $T_d = 125$ ms

Figure 45: Nyquist plots of RMS-based coupling for varying time delay with $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$ and $PF=0.95$

(a) $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.1$

(b) $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.2$

(c) $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.3$

Figure 46: Nyquist plots of RMS-based coupling for varying impedance ratio with $T_d = 25\text{ ms}$ and $PF=0.95$

(a) PF = 0.95

(b) PF = 0.75

(c) PF = 0.65

Figure 47: Nyquist plots of RMS-based coupling for varying PF with $T_d = 25$ ms and $Z_1/Z_2 = 0.25$

It is clear that the theoretical assessment results for both synchronous dq-based and asynchronous RMS-based GD-RTS setups by using the detailed models obtained completely comply with the simulation results in Matlab/Simulink which are shown in Figure 25. Differences are also caused by the individual transfer functions. For the former type, transfer function between input 1 and output 2 plays a key role while for the latter type, relation between input 1 and output 1 is crucial, in particular, Figure 41 vs Figure 45 for time delay, Figure 42 vs Figure 46 for impedance ration, and Figure 43 vs Figure 47 for power factor.

- *Influence of time delay (T_d):* The time delay shows a significant impact on the synchronous coupling with $T_d = 25$ ms being the boundary for its stability (Figure 41). On the other hand, it does not unfavourably impact the stability of the asynchronous coupling for values of T_d up to 125 ms (Figure 45).
- *Influence of impedance ratio (Z_1/Z_2):* Figure 42 and Figure 46 show much smaller stability margins for both GD-RTS setups, which is 0.3 in comparison to the conventional PHIL implementations, which is typically considered equal to 1. The results are fully consistent with those derived from simulation in Simulink provided in Figure 25b for synchronous and Figure 26b for asynchronous coupling types, respectively.
- *Influence of power factor (PF):* The stability assessment from the proposed models also show a reasonable compliance with the simulations results. The system is more sensitive with the lower PF.

4.5.6 Results

The overall boundaries derived from the stability analysis of both synchronous dq-based and asynchronous RMS-based coupling types are reported in Figure 48a and Figure 48b, respectively with regards to three main affecting factors namely time delay, impedance ratio, and PF. The vertical axis illustrates the variation of time delay on a logarithmic scale against the horizontal axis showing the variation of impedance ratio.

From the practical application perspective, each curve that corresponds to one value of PF divides the plane into stable and unstable areas. According to Figure 48a, for a specific value of PF, to attain a stable operation, the GD-RTS setup adopting synchronous coupling method should operate at a point whose time delay and impedance ratio values are located in the lower part of the respective curve; otherwise, any point located above this curve will make the setup unstable. Similarly, Figure 48a suggests that the GD-RTS setup using asynchronous coupling should ensure its time delay and impedance ratio located on the left side of the specific curve corresponding to the value of the H_{ul} power factor.

The results obtained from the joint research activities in this track were analysed in more detail and described systematically in (M. Syed et al., 2022). Moreover, a real-world RMS-based GD-RTS implementation between the Dynamic Power Systems Laboratory at the University of Strathclyde (Scotland) and the Electric Energy Systems Laboratory at the National Technical University of Athens (Greece) was carried out to validate the developed models and its results were also reported in this paper. The extensive investigation will support the user in gaining a general understanding of the applicability of GD-RTS and provide them a tool to evaluate and then realise multi-RI experimental setups coping with the increasing complexity of the modern power system.

(a) Synchronous dq-based coupling

(b) Asynchronous RMS-based coupling

Figure 48: Overall stability boundaries for different coupling types.

4.5.7 Further work

In the next sprint, the joint working team will focus on the development of a comprehensive procedure for the practical implementation of GD-RTS setups. This can be considered as a guide aiming at providing detailed step-by-step instruction in setting up the GD-RTS-based experiment. The document is anticipated to cover first the identification of the test scenario, followed by the selection of electrical interface, then the establishment of communication link, and last the safe initialisation of the experiment.

4.6 Accelerating Time-to-Experiment for Remote RI Coupling

In this track, new tools for the setup of large-scale distributed experiments involving multiple RIs in geographically separated locations have been developed.

4.6.1 Motivation

The complexity of large experimental setups is usually driven by the heterogeneous environment which is found in today's smart-grid laboratories.

4.6.2 Problem Statement

These tools aim to accelerate time-to-experiment by adopting software automation techniques and best practices used in Cloud computing for orchestrating complex experimental setups. Specifically, open-source container technology and the Kubernetes orchestration tool are employed to achieve a high degree of automation.

One central paradigm is the specification of an experimental setup using a machine-readable description which is consumed by the automation tools to setup the specified scenario. In cloud computing, this idea is often referred to as Infrastructure as Code (IaC).

4.6.3 Scope

In this track, a group of project members has been working during the first two sprints on a set of tools collectively named RIasC.

RIasC, an acronym for Research Infrastructure as Code, is a framework to accelerate distributed RI experiments. RIasC is composed of several tools and services which could also be used and developed independently. Collectively, they are managed under the umbrella of the Open-source project RIasC⁷ which is published under the Apache 2.0 license in the ERIGrid 2.0 GitHub organization⁸.

Inspired by the IaC paradigm, RIasC achieves a high degree of automation of common tasks in a research environment such as:

- Rapid deployment of controllers and other services in a research/laboratory cloud,
- Network setup and VPN configuration,
- Logging of research data,
- Formalization and declarative description of research experiments, and
- Emulation and monitoring of communication network characteristics.

IaC is the process of managing and provisioning computer data-centers through machine-readable definition files, rather than physical hardware configuration or interactive configuration tools. The IT infrastructure managed by this process comprises both physical equipment, such as bare-metal servers, as well as virtual machines, and associated configuration resources.

⁷<https://riasc.eu>

⁸<https://github.com/orgs/ERIGrid2/teams/riasc/repositories>

The definitions may be in a version control system. It can use either scripts or declarative definitions, rather than manual processes, but the term is more often used to promote declarative approaches.

RlasC provides the following functionalities to accelerate distributed Research Infrastructure (RI) experiments:

Provisioning of Mobile Units

A mobile unit in RlasC's terminology is a mobile computing device acting as a gateway between laboratory equipment and other possible remote laboratories. The setup and maintenance updates of the units are handled by RlasC to alleviate the researcher from a manual setup of these devices.

Deployment of Containerized Software Components

The mobile units run a Linux operating system and join a Kubernetes cluster which consists of all the mobile units. This Kubernetes cluster allows the researcher to declaratively describe the setup of software components which are executed as containerized applications on the cluster.

Transparent Inter-laboratory Overlay Network

Research of highly complex systems such as for example today's energy systems is increasingly undertaken by a group of researchers and institutions. Consequently, it is desirably to perform distributed experiments spanning multiple laboratories. RlasC simplifies the setup of such distributed setups by providing a transparent IP overlay network between all participating laboratories.

Time Synchronization

For GD-RTS, a common time-base is required in order to synchronize the simulation of coupled subsystems as well as the proper temporal alignment of simulation results. A time-synchronization service provides this common time-base by synchronizing the clock of each mobile-unit via one of the supported synchronization sources. The RlasC time-synchronization currently supports the Global Positioning System (GPS), the Network Time Protocol (NTP) or the Precision Time Protocol (PTP) as synchronization sources.

Network Emulation

Network emulation allows for a realistic emulation of real-world network characteristics. RlasC provides a network emulation service which allows the researcher to declaratively describe desired network parameters such as communication delay, packet loss, throughput etc.

Network Monitoring

In a geographically distributed experiment spanning across multiple laboratories, network characteristics are also affected by the communication link between the sites. In many cases this is the public Internet and/or the national research networks. These networks are shared mediums and as such can exhibit congestion and unpredictable latencies and packet loss. RlasC aims at counteracting these effects by providing a network monitoring service which monitors the network conditions between a configurable set of mobile-units. In a similar manner as the network emulation configuration, the scheduling of these monitoring tests can be configured declaratively.

At the time of writing this deliverable, the architecture network monitoring service has been defined. The implementation of this service has yet to start.

4.6.4 Approach

The acceleration of experiment setup times is achieved by increasing the degree of automation of lab configuration tasks and software deployment as well a selection of supportive services which have been described in the scope of this track.

4.6.5 Implementation

Figure 53 illustrates an exemplary setup of a RlasC cluster consisting of three laboratories and four Mobile Units (MUs) which are interconnected via a distributed Kubernetes cluster.

RlasC uses K3S⁹ as its Kubernetes distribution which is optimized for lightweight deployments on edge devices like a Raspberry Pi Single Board Computer (SBC). Each laboratory hosts one or more MUs which automatically register them self with the Kubernetes cluster.

To deploy a MU an existing desktop or server workstation could be used. But also more lightweight SBCs like the Raspberry can be used.

The requirements for running a K3S *agent* are relatively low. Both Intel/AMD x86 and ARM architectures supported. K3S has no other external dependencies besides the Linux kernel which simplifies the setup of a MU significantly.

All other software components and services are deployed and managed by Kubernetes which makes K3S the only software dependency which is installed by the provisioning system.

4.6.6 Results

Provisioning The provisioning component is responsible for quickly adding new MUs to the RlasC cluster with minimal manual effort. It is realized by the use of pre-configured system OS images for various environments.

New MUs can be automatically provisioned by booting them with such an image. Users only provide minimal configuration such as the IP addresses, host names or access tokens for registration to a RlasC cluster.

⁹<https://k3s.io>

```

---
apiVersion: device.riasc.eu/v1
kind: Chroma4Q
metadata:
  name: rwth-chroma
  namespace: sim-hes-off
spec:
  connection:
    host: chroma.acs-lab.eonerc.rwth-aachen.de
    port: 2101
    timeout: 20

  state: disconnected
  phases: [1, 2]

  parameters:
    maxCurrent: 16.0 # A
    overcurrentDelay: 0.0 # s
    maxPower: 3500 # VA
    maxFrequency: 55.0 # Hz
    maxVolageAC: 235.0 # V

  setpoints:
    voltageDC: [ 0.0, 0.0]
    voltageRMS: [230.0, 240.0]
    frequency: [ 50.0, 51.0]

```

Figure 49: Device Manifest.

Figure 50: Operator concept.

Figure 51: Operator Reconciliation Loop.

Figure 52: Helm Package Management for Kubernetes.

Figure 53: RlasC Cluster Example.

Figure 54: Provisioning flow.

Figure 54 shows the flow for generating and booting a pre-generated SD card image on the SBC.

We distinguish two groups of users or *roles* within a RlasC cluster:

Cluster operator oversees the administrative tasks of setting up a RlasC cluster and its central components (K3S server, Ansible repository, Access Control)

Lab provider participates in the RlasC cluster by providing one or more agent nodes which join the cluster.

There are three steps required for provisioning new nodes:

- **Generation of a new system image**

This step is usually only performed once by the cluster operator. It generates the new system image by embedding a special script named `riasc-update.sh` into the image which gets executed during every system boot.

- **Configuration**

Once the system image has been generated by the cluster operator and distributed to the lab providers, the lab providers need to customize the image by providing a few custom configuration settings like the agent host name, IP address or access tokens required for joining the cluster.

These settings are provided in a YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML)¹⁰ configuration file. In the case of a Raspberry Pi agent, this configuration resides on the FAT32-formatted `boot` partition and is therefore easily editable by Windows users as well.

- **First boot**

Once the configuration file has been edited by the user, the new agent can be booted for the first time by the lab provider. During this initial and all subsequent boots of the node a shell script named `riasc-update.sh` is executed. This shell script performs some initial checks, install some required software packages and performs some first basic configuration tasks like the setup of the system host name.

¹⁰<https://yaml.org/>

All further configuration is then handled by Ansible¹¹. Ansible is an open-source software provisioning, configuration management, and application-deployment tool enabling infrastructure as code. It runs on many Unix-like systems, and can configure both Unix-like systems as well as Microsoft Windows. It includes its own declarative language to describe system configuration.

The `riasc-update.sh` script uses the `ansible-pull` command to fetch the system configuration from a remote Git repository. Once fetched, the system configuration is applied and the new agent node is joined to the K3s Kubernetes cluster.

- **Subsequent boots** Once the initial boot has been completed, the provisioning process is completed. The cluster operator can now apply further updates to the agent by updating the Ansible repository and triggering a reboot of the node. Such a reboot will cause the `riasc-update.sh` script to be executed again and reapply the now possibly updated configuration.

Having embedded devices in a securely guarded lab-environment automatically executing code fetched from a remote repository is undoubtedly a security risk which needs to be mitigated. Hence, the `ansible-pull` command checks the fetched Git commit for an embedded Pretty Good Privacy (PGP) signature which is verified against a static white-list of PGP keys of the cluster operator.

Transparent Overlay Network Unlike in traditional cloud deployments, the participating agent nodes are usually not residing in the same network. As a consequence, direct communication between containers deployed on different agent nodes is not possible. To solve this restriction a transparent overlay network is established between all agent and master nodes. This overlay network employs Virtual Private Network (VPN) solutions to create a mesh of peer-to-peer connections between all nodes in the cloud. Within this overlay network all deployed containers are assigned an IP from the cluster internal subnet. Containers can use these addresses (and also Kubernetes *ClusterIPs*) to communicate with each other even if they are deployed on different nodes in different sites.

As the overlay network establishes connectivity between all nodes, the Kubernetes cluster networks can be used as on any other Kubernetes cluster. However, it is important to note that the overlay network only establishes connectivity between IPs/containers within the cluster. Connecting devices and services outside the cluster (e.g. in a dedicated laboratory network) is not supported by the overlay network.

Architecture The VPN is implemented by a newly developed tool named `cunīcu`¹².

`cunīcu` is a user-space daemon managing WireGuard™ interfaces to establish a mesh of peer-to-peer VPN connections in harsh network environments.

To achieve this, `cunīcu` utilizes a signaling layer to exchange peer information such as public encryption keys, hostname, advertised networks and reachability information to automate the configuration of the networking links. From a user perspective, `cunīcu` alleviates the need of manual configuration such as exchange of public keys, IP addresses and endpoints. Hence, it adopts the design goals of the WireGuard project, to be simple and easy to use.

¹¹<https://www.ansible.com/>

¹²<https://cunicu.li>

```
---
apiVersion: riasc.eu/v1
kind: Project
metadata:
  name: sim-hes-off
spec:
  users:
  - stv0g
  nodes:
  - rpi-rwth-1
```

Figure 55: Project Manifest.

Thanks to Interactive Connectivity Establishment (ICE), `cunīcu` is capable to establish direct connections between peers which are located behind Network Address Translation (NAT) firewalls such as home routers. In situations where ICE fails, or direct UDP connectivity is not available, `cunīcu` falls back to using Traversal Using Relays around NAT (TURN) relays to reroute traffic over an intermediate hop or encapsulate the WireGuard traffic via TURN-TCP.

It relies on the `pion/ice` package for ICE as well as bundles the Go user-space implementation of WireGuard in a single binary for systems in which WireGuard kernel support has not landed yet.

With these features, `cunīcu` can be used to quickly build multi-agent systems or connect field devices such as power grid monitoring infrastructure into a fully connected mesh. Within the ERIGrid 2.0 project, `cunīcu` is used to interconnect smart grid laboratories for geographically distributed simulation of energy systems.

Project-based Access Control

Network Emulation `k8s-netem`¹³ adds traffic control to Kubernetes pods.

It allows the user to configure one or more traffic profiles to impair network traffic between pods in the cluster and between pods and external networks.

The traffic profiles are implemented as a Custom Resource (CR) which the user can add and modify in the Kubernetes database using standard tools like `kubect1` or a Kubernetes web-interface.

These, *TrafficProfiles* can use `podSelectors` or Classless Inter-domain Routing (CIDR)ś to match a set of source and destination pods/networks for which the impairment should be configured. In addition the impairment can be restricted to a set of UDP or TCP port numbers.

The traffic profile custom resource is heavily inspired by Kubernetes *NetworkPolicy* CR.

¹³<http://github.com/erigrid2/k8s-netem>

```

---
apiVersion: k8s-netem.riasc.eu/v1
kind: TrafficProfile
metadata:
  name: profile-delay-jitter
spec:
  podSelector:
    matchLabels:
      application: py_ctrl
  type: Builtin
  parameters:
    netem:
      delay: 0.2 # seconds
      jitter: 0.05
      loss_ratio: 1 # in [0, 1]
      distribution: "normal"

```

Figure 56: TrafficProfile Manifest.

Network Monitoring One of the objectives of RlasC is the facilitation of distributed experiments such as for example GD-RTS. This is enabled by the interconnection of research infrastructures between different organisations, countries and even continents which host digital real-time simulators and/or controller/power HIL setups.

Among other services, RlasC provides an transparent overlay network to establish Internet Protocol (IP) connectivity between the locations. This IP overlay network is established via a peer-to-peer topology. Meaning, as long as permitted by network policies, traffic will be exchanged directly between each of the labs rather than being routed over a central VPN gateway. In cases where direct communication is blocked, traffic is rerouted over a third party. Hence, from a user perspective, all participating laboratories appear to connected to the same local network.

However, due to the geographical distances between them a considerable communication latency exists. To compensate the effect of these increased communication latencies, an IA is required.

In most cases the IA requires the current communication network state as an input.

For this purpose, RlasC implements network monitoring which periodically monitors several network metrics such as bandwidth, latency, packet loss, etc.

The network monitoring feature of RlasC is based on the established perfSONAR¹⁴ tool suite and adapts it for its usage in a Kubernetes cluster. This includes the deployment of perfSONAR core components in the cluster itself as well as the execution of perfSONAR testpoints on the agent nodes throughout the participating RIs. Last but not least, a dedicated Kubernetes operator is used to manage test schedules by the means of Kubernetes Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs).

Time Synchronization This paragraph describes the steps to setup time-synchronization for embedded SBCs such as a Raspberry Pi. The time-synchronization relies on a commodity GPS

¹⁴<https://www.perfsonar.net/>

Figure 57: perfSONAR architecture.

```

---
apiVersion: riasec.eu/v1
kind: SchedulerConfig
metadata:
  name: test
spec:
  groups:
    latency_group:
      type: mesh
      addresses:
        - name: rpi-rwth-1
        - name: ntnu-1
  tests:
    latency_test:
      type: latencybg
      spec:
        source: "{%_address [0] _%}"
        dest: "{%_address [1] _%}"
        packet-interval: 0.1
        packet-count: 600

```

Figure 58: SchedulerConfig Manifest.

module providing a Pulse-per-Second (PPS) output to a General Purpose Input/Output (GPIO) pin of the SBC.

Time-synchronization is implemented by a cluster-wide *DaemonSet* which spawns a single *Pod* on each of the cluster nodes.

These *Pods* execute three containers:

chronyd

status

gpsd

All containers in the *Pod* communicate via sockets which are placed into a shared `emptyDir` volume.

There are three sockets created:

- `gpsd` → `chronyd` coarse date-time: `/run/chrony.ttyAMA0.sock`
- `gpsd` → `chronyd` precise PPS timing: `/run/chrony.pps0.sock`
- `status` → `chronyd` status reporting: `/run/chrony`

All sockets are created by `chronyd` and sub-sequentially opened by `gpsd` and the `status.py` script. The first two sockets are used to provide rough date-time as well as PPS timing information from `gpsd` to `chronyd`. The last socket is usually used by the `chronyc` command line tool to interact with the `chronyd` daemon. Here the socket is also used by the `status.py` script to periodically check the sync status and publish it to the Kubernetes Application Programming Interface (API)-server.

In addition to the shared sockets, some physical devices are mounted from the host into the containers using a `hostPath` volume. The `gpsd` container gets both the serial device `/dev/ttyAMA0` as well as the `/dev/pps0` device mounted. The `chronyd` container only gets the PPS device `/dev/pps0` mounted.

Linux kernel-level PPS device Both `gpsd` and `chronyd` use the kernel-based PPS device order for the PPS `/dev/pps0` device to be created a special device tree overlay needs to be loaded during boot-up.

Status reporting As mentioned above a dedicated `status` container in the time-sync *Pods* is used to periodically publish the current synchronization state from `chronyd` in the form of a *Node status-condition* to the Kubernetes API-server.

This container runs a Python script¹⁵ which periodically calls the `chronyc tracking` and `chronyc sources` commands to query the current synchronization status. Afterwards, the script will publish this status as *Node status-condition* to the Kubernetes API-server as well include more details a annotations to the *Node* resource.

`k8s-netem` uses the following synchronization sources in the order of their priority:

1. Pulse-per-Second (PPS) signal¹⁶
 - Kernel-based PPS (kPPS)

¹⁵https://github.com/ERIGrid2/riasc-operator/blob/master/src/time_sync/status.py

¹⁶https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Pulse-per-second_signal

```
---
apiVersion: riasc.eu/v1
kind: TimeSyncConfig
metadata:
  name: aurelius
spec:
  nodeSelector:
    kubernetes.io/hostname: rpi-aurelius-4
  ntp:
    server:
      enabled: true
      local: true
      stratum: 1
      allow:
        - 172.23.157.0/24
  gps:
    enabled: true
    device: ttyAMA0
  pps:
    enabled: true
    device: pps0
    pin: 18
```

Figure 59: TimeSyncConfig Manifest.

- User-space PPS
2. Precision Time Protocol (PTP)¹⁷
 3. Network Time Protocol (NTP)¹⁸
 4. System Real-time Clock (RTC)¹⁹

4.6.7 Further work

During the first half of the ERIGrid 2.0 project, Track 2.5 has laid out the foundation for the development of an ERIGrid 2.0 middleware by providing the necessary IT infrastructure for running highly distributed experiments in an extended RI. The development of RlasC will be continued by integrating it with other services such as configuration and data management. As part of the demonstration activities later in the project, the benefits of RlasC will be demonstrated and evaluated in a multi-RI use case. While the development and documentation of most of the services presented in this section have been concluded, the network monitoring service is still under active development in the ongoing sprint. Further testing and iterative improvements to the software base are expected to be applied continuously.

¹⁷https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Precision_Time_Protocol

¹⁸https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Network_Time_Protocol

¹⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Real-time_clock

5 Conclusions

5.1 Main Findings

The broad topical range of coupling methods for RI testing and validation methodologies in ERIGrid 2.0 has been divided into eight separate work tracks, each with a well-defined scope. Most of the eight work tracks have arrived at the proof-of-concept stage, typically using a “minimum viable product” approach. The headline results from all tracks can be summarized as follows:

- *Track 1.1:* The track has developed two FMI 3.0-compliant FMUs representing simple two-node communication network models and subsequently mapped the FMI 3.0 event model to the new Mosaik 3 API. An implementation based on a simple test case has been used to demonstrate a FMI 3.0-based co-simulation between three FMUs representing a LV distribution grid, a transformer tap controller, and the aforementioned communication network model.
- *Track 1.2:* The thermal network benchmark developed earlier in ERIGrid 2.0, consisting of a thermal network, a LV power distribution grid and a power-to-heat facility, has been analysed using a co-simulation approach based on the Mosaik co-simulation framework, using two different thermal network simulators, the pandapipes package and the DisHeatLib library. Both implementations differ considerably, but the resulting network dynamics are comparable both qualitatively and quantitatively.
- *Track 1.3:* The track has tested the ability of the superdense time approach in the Mosaik co-simulation environment to resolve simulation initialisation problems caused by cyclic dependencies, using same-time loops. The test involved the multi-energy network benchmark model earlier developed in ERIGrid 2.0. The efficacy of the same time loop approach is clearly distinguishable in the results, causing the controller in the test case to be initialised correctly and removing numerical artefacts from the initial system response.
- *Track 2.1:* The track has identified a need for the collection of real-world performance data on networks interconnecting research infrastructures. It has devised a measurement approach which is to be executed in subsequent sprints.
- *Track 2.2:* The performance of two types of interface algorithms for GD-RTS have been analysed and compared: A synchronous coupling approach using direct-quadrature-zero (dq0) transformation and an asynchronous coupling approach using RMS. The applicability of GD-RTS was verified based on an actual experimental setup between two partner infrastructures.
- *Track 2.3:* The track has developed a framework for pre-determining or estimating robustness and sensitivity properties of PHIL systems in an analytical way. The framework has been validated against selected case studies, using both purely analytical models as well as experimental setups. Using the results of both types of case studies, the validation process of the framework for sensitivity analysis could be performed by comparing either analytical or experimental results with developed metrics of the sensitivity framework. Results confirm that the validation process has been successfully performed for different types of PHIL systems.
- *Track 2.4:* The track analysed the stability of geographically distributed real-time simulations in the presence of network time delays, both for synchronous dq-based and asynchronous RMS-based couplings. The results were described systematically in a publica-

tion. A real-world test implementation between two partner laboratories was carried out to validate the developed models.

- *Track 2.5:* The track has developed a deployable suite of tools (i.e., RlasC) to simplify and standardise the setup of geographically distributed experiments between multiple RI. Features include automated provisioning, configuration and the establishment of a transparent overlay network. A prototype of RlasC has been successfully tested against multiple RIs.

5.2 Further Work

The logical next steps for the individual tracks are:

- A move to more complex study cases (Tracks 1.1 and 2.2),
- Incremental improvements to models and tools (Tracks 1.2 and 2.5),
- Testing and documentation (Tracks 1.3 and 2.5),
- Experimental validation (Tracks 2.2 and 2.3), and
- Moving from a concept towards a first implementation (Tracks 2.1 and 2.4).

While all work tracks have a defined direction and a roadmap for the next steps, the target goal of each track will not be defined internally in this work. Ultimately, the results of work are meant to be demonstrated later on in ERIGrid 2.0. Therefore, the needs of these demonstrations will define the track goals, once they have been defined in collaboration with the demonstration activity.

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